

D5.3 – Report on Integrating Gender Perspectives into EUA recommendations for Energy Research, Innovation, Education

WP5 – Development of credible pathways for equitable, just, and fair energy transitions

Contributors	Dr Yara Evans, Imperial College Dr Rocio Diaz-Chavez, Imperial College
Reviewers	Marco Cellini Pauline Sekula Clemens Striebing Aleksandra Wagner
Delivery date	31/07/2025
Dissemination level	Public

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GeneSys (Transforming Gendered Interrelations of Power and Inequalities in Transition Pathways to Sustainable Energy Systems) has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe - Culture, creativity and inclusive society - under grant agreement no. 101094326. "UK participants in Horizon Europe Project (gEneSys) GA. 101094326 are supported by UKRI grant number 10061890 (Imperial College London). Project gEneSys is funded by the European Union under Horizon Europe Grant Agreement No. 101094326. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or UKRI. Neither the European Union nor UKRI can be held responsible for them."

<i>Project Acronym</i>	<i>gEneSys</i>
<i>Agreement number</i>	101094326
<i>Project Full Title</i>	<i>gEneSys - Transforming Gendered Interrelations of Power and Inequalities in Transition Pathways to Sustainable Energy Systems</i>
<i>Funding Scheme</i>	Horizon Europe

Deliverable Information

<i>Deliverable Name</i>	<i>Report on Gender in EUA recommendations for R&I and Education</i>
<i>Dissemination level</i>	Public (PU)
<i>Funding Scheme</i>	Horizon Europe
<i>Grant Agreement number</i>	101094326
<i>Contractual date of delivery</i>	31 July 2025
<i>Deliverable Leader</i>	Imperial College
<i>WP/Task Responsible</i>	Imperial College
<i>Keywords</i>	GI, SHAPE Lexicon, gender, energy, energy transition, interdisciplinarity
<i>Abstract</i>	This report uses SHAPE and GIA frameworks to assess the integration of gender and interdisciplinarity in energy education. It first codes MSc energy-related courses in Italy, Germany, Poland, and the UK, revealing a strong STEM dominance, exclusionary entry requirements, weak interdisciplinarity, and near-total absence of gender perspectives. It then applies the same frameworks to the EUA 2017 recommendations on energy education and innovation, which, while promoting systems thinking and societal engagement, largely overlook gender and lack concrete mechanisms for interdisciplinary integration. The comparison highlights a clear disconnect between policy ambition and educational practice. The combined findings highlight the value of redesigning curricula and policy using SHAPE and GIA to help ensure that energy education supports inclusive participation and addresses the social dimensions of energy transitions.

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Document history

<i>Date</i>	<i>Version</i>	<i>Authors</i>
	Draft	Yara Evans; Rocio Diaz-Chavez
<i>Date</i>	<i>Version</i>	<i>Reviewers</i>
	Draft	Marco Cellini
	Draft	Pauline Sekula
	Draft	Clemens Striebing
	Draft	Aleksandra Wagner

Contents

LIST OF TABLES	2
ACRONYMS	3
1. INTRODUCTION	4
2. GENDER AND ENERGY IN HIGHER EDUCATION	5
3. SHAPE AND ITS LEXICON	7
4. THE GENDER INNOVATIONS APPROACH	8
5. SHAPE AND GIA INTO MSC ENERGY COURSES	10
5.1 Applying SHAPE and GIA to MSc Energy Courses in gEneSys Countries	11
6. ORIGINS, AIMS, AND STRATEGIC CONTEXT OF THE 2017 EUA ENERGY TRANSITION AGENDA	24
6.1 SHAPE AND GIA INTO EUA ERIE RECOMMENDATIONS	26
6.2 Integrating SHAPE and GIA into EUA ERIE Recommendations	27
7. REASSESSING ERIE: THE ROLE OF SHAPE AND GIA	36
8. ADVANCING RRI IN ERIE: THE ROLE OF SHAPE AND GIA	37
9. INTERDISCIPLINARITY AS A PATHWAY TO GENDER-EQUITABLE ENERGY TRANSITIONS	38
10. STRENGTHENING EUA’S FUTURE THROUGH GENDER-RESPONSIVE ERIE	39
11. CONCLUSION	50
12. REFERENCES	51
APPENDIX I	58
APPENDIX II	60
APPENDIX III	74

LIST OF TABLES

TABLE 1 SHAPE LEXICON KEYWORDS 7

TABLE 2 GIA METHODOLOGIES AND THEIR APPLICATION IN THE FIELD OF ENERGY 8

TABLE 3 ANALYSIS OF MSC ENERGY COURSES: ITALY 14

TABLE 4 ANALYSIS OF MSC ENERGY COURSES: GERMANY 16

TABLE 5 ANALYSIS OF MSC ENERGY COURSES: POLAND 19

TABLE 6 ANALYSIS OF MSC ENERGY COURSES: THE UK 21

TABLE 7 ANALYS OF MSC ENERGY COURSES IN GENESYS COUNTRIES 23

TABLE 8 EUA CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITIES FOR FUTURE ERIE..... 24

TABLE 9 EUA ERIE RECOMMENDATIONS BY STRAND 25

TABLE 10 STEPS FOR APPLYING SHAPE AND GIA TO THE EUA RECOMMENDATIONS 27

TABLE 11 ANALYSIS OF EUA ERIE RECOMMENDATIONS..... 27

TABLE 12 SAMPLE OF SHAPE/GIA CODED EUA RECOMMENDATIONS FOR EACH STRAND 29

TABLE 13 LITERATURE SUPPORTING THE SHAPE/GIA CODING OF EUA RECOMMENDATIONS 31

ACRONYMS

EC	European Commission
ERIE	Energy Research and Innovation and Education
EU	European Union
EUA	European University Association
GIA	Gendered Innovations Approach
HE	Higher Education
MSc	Master of Science postgraduate degree
R&I	Research and Innovation
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals
SET-Plan	Strategic Energy Technology Plan
SHAPE	Social Sciences, Humanities and the Arts for People and the Economy
SLR	Systematic Literature Review
SSH	Social Sciences and Humanities
STEM	Science, Technology, Engineering, Mathematics
UNIT-SET	Universities in the SET-Plan

1. INTRODUCTION

This report presents the work conducted for Task 5.3 of Work Package 5 in the gEneSys project. gEneSys aims to advance understanding of the gender dimension in energy research, innovation, and socio-economic development to support more just and inclusive sustainable energy systems, and to address gender inequalities in energy transitions. Central to this vision is the conceptualisation of the energy transition as a dynamic, mission-oriented, and gendered socio-technical innovation ecosystem. This ecosystem encompasses interdependent technological, social, environmental, governance, and economic subsystems shaped by sustainability goals, actors, power relations, and institutional contexts. Recognising the importance of equity and diversity in shaping these subsystems, Work Package 5 aims to identify gender biases and evidence gaps in current energy research and education systems, and to propose approaches that ensure women and marginalised groups can fully participate in and benefit from socio-technical transformations.

Figure 1 gEneSys Conceptualisation of Energy Transition

Task 5.3 contributes to these goals by investigating the extent to which gender and interdisciplinarity are incorporated into current policy and educational practice in energy research and innovation. Specifically, the task analyses the recommendations published by the European University Association (EUA, 2017) on Energy Research and Innovation and Education (ERIE). Although these recommendations align with the EU's broad emphasis on interdisciplinarity, stakeholder engagement, and innovation, they remain largely silent on gender equality, gender analysis, and intersectional inclusion. To address this silence, this report applies two methodological frameworks: SHAPE (Social sciences, Humanities, and the Arts for People and the Economy) and GIA (Gender Innovations Approach) to code and critically assess the EUA recommendations across four key thematic strands: General, Energy Efficiency, Smart and Grid Systems, and Renewable Energy Integration. The aim is to explore how the inclusion of gender and interdisciplinarity can strengthen the recommendations, enhance their societal relevance, and contribute to a more just and inclusive energy transition.

To address these gaps, the report introduces the SHAPE and GIA frameworks as methodological tools for analysing both educational content and policy guidance. The report proposes using these frameworks to apply structured coding to a sample of MSc programmes as well as the EUA recommendations, to highlight where gendered, social, and interdisciplinary dimensions could be

meaningfully integrated. By bringing these frameworks into dialogue with a critical reading of MSc programmes and the recommendations in the EUA Action Agenda, the report aims to generate insights into how energy education and research agendas can be aligned with broader goals for gender justice and social inclusion. The analysis also supports and feeds into other workstreams of the gEneSys project, such as Task 3.4 on promoting gender-sensitive approaches in Higher Education (HE) and Task 5.5 on identifying inclusive innovation priorities for achieving Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 7.

This report is organised into two main parts. The first part begins by outlining persistent gaps in how gender and interdisciplinarity are addressed in HE related to energy. It then introduces the two analytical frameworks, SHAPE and GIA, which are used to assess the integration of gender and social dimensions in both academic and policy contexts. Next, the report sets out the rationale, objectives, methodology, and findings from the application of SHAPE and GIA coding to a purposive sample of MSc energy-related programmes offered in four gEneSys partner countries: Italy, Germany, Poland, and the UK. This section details how course titles, departmental affiliations, curricula content, and entry requirements of a sample of courses from each country either support or neglect interdisciplinarity and gender inclusion, providing insights into how current educational structures may shape access, participation, and equity within the energy sector. These findings help identify the structural and cultural patterns that influence inclusivity in energy education. As such, they lay important groundwork for the second part of the report, which examines how similar dynamics play out at the policy level through an analysis of EUA ERIE recommendations.

The second part of the report shifts focus to the 2017 EUA ERIE recommendations. It applies the same SHAPE and GIA frameworks to four thematic strands of the EUA recommendations: General, Energy Efficiency, Smart and Grid Systems, and Renewable Energy Integration. The section first introduces the rationale for this coding exercise. Next, it presents the key results, revealing where gender and interdisciplinary considerations are missing or need to be enhanced. This is followed by a brief comparative analysis between the MSc course findings and the EUA policy recommendations to highlight systemic gaps as well as areas of potential alignment. The report further discusses how integrating SHAPE and GIA into both curricula and policy enhances the principles of Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI), thereby strengthening higher education's role in advancing gender-equitable energy transitions. The report concludes with targeted recommendations to improve EUA future work and guidance and to embed gender inclusion and interdisciplinarity more systematically across European ERIE.

2. GENDER AND ENERGY IN HIGHER EDUCATION

Despite increasing awareness of the need for inclusive and socially responsive approaches to energy transitions, higher education energy curricula remain predominantly technology-focused, prioritising STEM content over social sciences and gender perspectives. Studies by Mahajan and Bandyopadhyay (2021), Mininni (2022), and Ockwell et al. (2018) reveal that gender and intersectionality are frequently treated as peripheral or elective topics, rather than embedded within the core epistemological and institutional frameworks of MSc and postgraduate programs. Musango and Bassi (2021) and Standal et al. (2020) further highlight how interdisciplinarity is often superficial, limiting sustained cross-disciplinary collaboration. This technical emphasis neglects the

complex socio-technical realities of energy systems and restricts the ability of education to attract diverse students and address broader social challenges inherent to energy transitions.

A significant but overlooked dimension of gender inequity is academic authorship and knowledge production. Allen et al. (2019) analyse over 140,000 US energy research articles from 1970 to 2016, revealing persistent underrepresentation of women, especially in leadership roles such as first and senior authorship, with pronounced disparities in technical fields such as petroleum engineering. While women's participation has increased in interdisciplinary and environmental journals, their work tends to receive fewer citations, especially when authored exclusively by women, reflecting systemic biases in recognition and influence. These female authors often focus on sustainability, social science, and environmental justice which are areas undervalued by engineering-focused higher education institutions. Allen et al. (2019) argue for structural reforms in publishing, funding, and mentorship to enhance gender equity, underscoring the need for frameworks such as SHAPE and GIA to transform research cultures and knowledge production alongside curricula.

This marginalisation of gender and interdisciplinarity is a global challenge. Studies from Pakistan (Ahmer, 2021) and the Middle East and North Africa (Fathallah & Pyakurel, 2020) show limited incorporation of gender-sensitive pedagogies and intersectional curricula, often lacking clear methodologies for effective integration. In Central and Eastern Europe, Kowalska et al. (2022) reveal gender differences in household energy behaviour, underscoring the need for empirical social science data to develop gender-responsive curricula. Bogovac et al. (2021) document how cultural norms and socio-economic factors further restrict girls' participation in STEM and energy education in Croatia. In Asia, Chen et al. (2015) and Irie and Kawahara (2021) demonstrate gendered differences in energy literacy and sustainability values, stressing the importance of holistic, gender-aware pedagogies. These studies further stress the urgent need for structured frameworks such as SHAPE and GIA to embed gender and social concerns systematically.

Research from Northern Europe, Africa, and the Americas reinforces this conclusion. Ring et al. (2022) reveal how masculine institutional cultures in Sweden perpetuate barriers to women's participation in engineering and energy careers despite formal equality policies. Pailman and de Groot (2022) find that African universities treat gender superficially, limiting integration across curricula and faculty development, though some interdisciplinary initiatives linking gender, energy justice, and climate resilience show promise. In Latin America and North America, Rincon-Flores et al. (2020) and Peña et al. (2021) highlight systemic neglect of women's experiences in energy community engagement and innovation systems, emphasising the critical role of gender-sensitive and interdisciplinary frameworks. In aggregate these global patterns demonstrate that gender and intersectionality remain marginalised in energy education and research worldwide.

This review therefore reveals that energy curricula remain heavily weighted toward technical STEM content, often overlooking the social realities and inequalities embedded in energy systems. The fragmented and superficial approach to interdisciplinarity and gender inclusion may thus weaken the fundamental role of higher education of preparing graduates capable of leading just and inclusive energy transitions. SHAPE and GIA frameworks offer essential, evidence-based methodologies for systematically integrating social sciences, humanities, gender, and intersectional analysis into energy education, research, and innovation. Their application promises to transform curricula, institutional cultures, and research priorities, fostering more inclusive, responsive, and socially robust energy education systems. Integrating gender into ERIE is therefore imperative to advance equitable and effective energy transitions that reflect and address the needs of diverse societies across the globe.

3. SHAPE AND ITS LEXICON

The SHAPE initiative emerged as a response to the growing recognition that energy challenges are not solely technical or economic but deeply embedded in social, cultural, political, and ethical contexts (Foulds & Robison, 2017). Funded under the EU Horizon 2020 programme, SHAPE aims to integrate Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) perspectives more fully into energy research and policy. The creation of the SHAPE Energy Lexicon was a pioneering effort within this initiative to clarify and bridge terminological differences in energy-related SSH concepts. It arose from an interdisciplinary workshop involving leading European energy scholars from fields such as Sociology, Political Science, Economics, Ethics, Communication Studies, and Anthropology, among others. This lexicon was designed to illuminate the diverse meanings attributed to 20 carefully selected energy-related keywords, fostering shared understanding across disciplines and sectors to enhance collaboration and policy relevance (Foulds & Robison, 2017).

The 20 keywords within the SHAPE Energy Lexicon encapsulate core SSH themes critical to understanding and addressing energy transitions (Table 1). These include concepts such as energy behaviour, energy citizen(ship), energy culture(s), energy governance, energy justice, energy policy, and energy transition, as well as more technical-social hybrid terms such as smart and sociotechnical. Each keyword is unpacked through multiple disciplinary lenses to reflect the variety of interpretations and emphases, from the micro-level actions of individuals and communities to the macro-level structures of institutions and governance¹. For example, energy justice addresses fairness in energy access and impacts, while energy citizenship highlights the active role of people in shaping energy futures beyond mere consumption. The lexicon underscores that words in energy discourse do not merely describe phenomena but shape research priorities, policy design, and public engagement (Foulds & Robison, 2017).

Table 1 SHAPE lexicon keywords

1. Energy behaviour	11. Energy poverty
2. Energy citizen (ship)	12. Energy practice(s)
3. Energy consumer	13. Energy security
4. Energy culture(s)	14. Energy social science
5. Energy efficiency	15. Energy storage
6. Energy future(s)	16. Energy transition
7. Energy governance	17. Energy engagement
8. Energy justice	18. Low-carbon energy
9. Energy models	19. Smart
10. Energy policy	20. Socio-technical

Source: Foulds & Robison (2017)

Applying the SHAPE lexicon to MSc energy courses offers a valuable means giving a sense of to what extent and how effectively social science and humanities dimensions are integrated into postgraduate energy education. Since energy transitions are deeply embedded in societal contexts, MSc programmes that address issues such as governance, justice, behaviour, and cultural change are likely to be better equipped to prepare graduates for real-world complexity. The SHAPE

¹ The origins, definitions, understandings and discussion of the keywords in the SHAPE lexicon are provided in Foulds & Robison (2017)

framework provides a structured vocabulary to identify whether and how such interdisciplinary and socially grounded themes are reflected in course content, departmental orientations, and entry pathways. Hence, applying the SHAPE lexicon to MSc energy courses can not only help reveal existing gaps but may also highlight opportunities to design more inclusive and socially responsive curricula. Building on this, the SHAPE lexicon is highly apposite for analysing the EUA’s recommendations across its four socio-technical strands, helping ensure that they become informed by the same nuanced understanding of social dynamics as the educational programmes intended to implement them (Foulds & Robison, 2017). Thus, SHAPE can play an important role in helping enhance the coherence and social robustness of the EUA’s vision, driving forward innovation and teaching that are ethically grounded, inclusive, and aligned with the lived realities of diverse energy users and stakeholders.

4. THE GENDER INNOVATIONS APPROACH

The GIA emerged from the groundbreaking *Gendered Innovations* project hosted at Stanford University since 2009. Its aim was to demonstrate how integrating sex and gender analysis into research improves the quality, accuracy, and social relevance of outcomes across STEM and SSH too (Schiebinger 2014,2021; GI 2025). GIA is grounded in feminist science and technology studies and has evolved into a comprehensive approach that also incorporates intersectionality. This means it recognises how gender interacts with other social categories (e.g., race, class, ethnicity, etc) to shape innovation processes and research outcomes (Wizemann & Pardue, 2001; Schiebinger, 2014). More recent iterations of the approach have focused on translating these principles into practical methodologies and tools that researchers and institutions can use to embed gender and intersectionality systematically in their work, thereby promoting more inclusive and socially responsible science (Schiebinger, 2021; GI, 2025).

At the core of the GIA is a commitment to transforming the entire research process, from how questions are framed to how knowledge is produced and communicated. It calls for a rethinking of conceptual frameworks, research designs, and data interpretation to avoid biased assumptions and ensure that diverse perspectives are reflected (Heidari et al., 2019; Schiebinger, 2021). The GIA also promotes participatory, reflexive, and inclusive approaches that challenge traditional hierarchies in research institutions. It positions gender analysis not as an add-on, but as an integral aspect of responsible and impactful innovation. This holistic vision expands the focus of analysis to include language, visual representation, ethical frameworks, and stakeholder engagement, reinforcing science’s societal relevance and ethical foundations (Schiebinger 2014, 2019). To operationalise these principles, the GIA outlines specific methodologies, as shown in Table 2. They are assigned a letter here for easier reference and for aiding the coding exercise of MSc energy programmes and the EUA ERIE recommendations that will be discussed later. Their description spells out what they entail when applied to the specific context of research on energy transitions.

Table 2 GIA Methodologies and their application in the field of energy

Method	Description
A	Rethinking research priorities and outcomes considering whether gender differences are relevant; particularly important in the context of energy transition when assembling the evidence base to support analysis of individual subsystems and their interactions with one another
B	Rethinking concepts and theories unpicking definitions (e.g., “energy transition”) and clarifying understanding of the wording used when energy transition is debated (e.g., “just transition”; “energy poverty”)

Report on Gender Perspectives into EUA Recommendations on Energy R&I and Education

to help understand the influence of formal and informal social institutions, social norms, and gender stereotypes of human behaviour

C *Formulating research questions*

scoping the analytical approach to identify gender-related power hierarchies in energy systems (traditional and emerging); relevant gender questions include ‘how to ensure societal acceptance of radical innovations and understand impacts of environmental degradation of energy infrastructures on women’s livelihoods and health’

D *Analysing sex*

paying attention to essential, unchangeable biological differences and how they influence response to energy poverty, hunger, disease, or changes in environmental conditions (e.g., due to polluting household cooking equipment)

E *Analysing gender*

understanding socio-cultural norms and stereotypes used in society to label an individual as male or female and recognising how socio-cultural differences and inequalities between women and men are maintained by social institutions

F *Analysing how sex and gender interact*

combining biological and socio-cultural perspectives on the role and behaviours of women and men (e.g., tracking impact of greenhouse gas emissions may involve understanding the gendered nature of energy consumption as it relates to work, or within the household, and how it relates to health and wellbeing)

G *Intersectional approaches*

paying attention to other human characteristics such as age, social status, education, ethnicity, race, geography, that play a role in defining vulnerability through lack of access to energy supply

H *Engineering Innovation Processes*

creating socio-technical systems to ensure that energy transition pathways and low-carbon technologies do not propagate gender inequalities embedded in existing technologies (e.g., solar panels are particularly difficult to dismantle, which makes attempts to recycle the components very difficult, contributing to accumulation of electronic waste, but also restricting opportunities for creating employment for women in electronic waste processing sector)

I *Co-creation and Participatory Research*

involving multiple actors and stakeholders in analysis of problems and generation of proposals for solutions, including the voices of rural, poor, indigenous, or other marginalised communities

J *Rethinking Standards and Reference Models*

removing gender bias in energy transition where transparency and traceability in procurement of resources, products, and services is needed (e.g., to ensure availability and price of energy)

K *Rethinking Language and Visual Representations*

demonstrating the gendered nature of energy transition in a way that can be easily comprehended by non-gender experts and lay persons (e.g., using images, graphics, stories when communicating rationales for gendered energy transitions)

Source: gEneSys (2024, adapted from GI, 2024/2025)

Applied to energy transitions, these GIA methodologies offer substantial potential to enhance the

integration of gender and intersectionality into ERIE. For example, Method A encourages institutions to prioritise energy justice and equitable access as central concerns. Methods C and F emphasise the refinement of research questions and the importance of nuanced data analysis that recognises gender differences and interactions. Method G further extends this by incorporating multiple dimensions of identity that influence individuals' experiences with energy systems. Collectively, these approaches strengthen research by grounding it in the lived realities of diverse societies, thereby ensuring that outcomes are both meaningful and impactful (Crenshaw, 1989; Schiebinger, 2021). Moreover, GIA methodology includes critical interrogation of norms and benchmarks that may reflect male-biased assumptions, as seen in Method I. Method J focuses on assessing the inclusivity or exclusivity of communication materials and curricula, while Method K encourages scrutiny of how knowledge is framed, validated, and disseminated. These strategies are especially important for energy education and innovation, where systemic and often unrecognised gender exclusion persists. By reshaping knowledge systems, GIA can help dismantle structural barriers and promote a more inclusive academic and professional environment for future energy leaders.

When used together, these GIA methodologies provide a robust framework for integrating gender and intersectionality into higher education and research on energy, ensuring both methodological rigour and social relevance. Embedding GIA into MSc energy curricula and the EUA's strategic recommendations represents a significant step towards inclusive, responsible, and socially aware energy transitions. This integration can enable higher education institutions to evaluate whether access criteria, course design, and institutional cultures support gender equality and inclusive participation. It may also assist the EUA in ensuring that its strategic research and innovation goals incorporate gender sensitivity, preventing the perpetuation of blind spots that exclude marginalised groups. Ultimately, this alignment supports the principles of Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI), which emphasise responsiveness to societal needs and values (Burget et al., 2017), preparing graduates to lead energy transitions that are not only innovative but also equitable and just.

5. SHAPE AND GIA INTO MSC ENERGY COURSES

The exercise of applying SHAPE and GIA coding to MSc energy programmes in gEneSys partner countries reflects a growing awareness that Europe's energy transition must be underpinned by educational frameworks that are inclusive, socially grounded, and capable of addressing the dynamic interactions between technical systems and human values. The SHAPE framework, which incorporates the contributions of SSH, offers a means to gauge whether MSc programmes meaningfully engage with broader societal concerns such as energy justice, public participation, policy integration, and future imaginaries. Complementing this, the GIA provides a systematic approach for analysing whether and how gender and diversity are integrated into curricula, research framing, and institutional structures. Together, SHAPE and GIA allow for a more nuanced and critical examination of curricular frameworks beyond surface-level claims of interdisciplinarity or inclusivity.

To establish a foundation for the subsequent SHAPE and GIA coding of the 2017 EUA recommendations, the report first presents an exploratory exercise that applies these frameworks to a purposive sample of MSc energy-related programmes in four gEneSys project countries: Italy, Germany, Poland, and the UK. This analysis aims to explore the extent to which postgraduate energy courses incorporate interdisciplinary perspectives and gender-sensitive approaches. By using the SHAPE lexicon, the exercise identifies whether key socio-technical issues such as

sustainability, behavioural change, and governance are reflected in course titles, departmental orientations, or teaching content. In parallel, the GIA framework is employed to assess whether courses explicitly address gender, intersectionality, and social inclusion, thereby providing an indication of their readiness to support equitable participation and leadership in energy transitions. These tools enable a structured comparison of whether and how social and gender dimensions are integrated in a sample of current programme design and pedagogical practice across different institutional and national contexts. This sequencing reinforces the report's core objective: to strengthen the links between educational practice and strategic policy to better align with the goals of a just, inclusive, and effective energy transition in Europe.

5.1 Applying SHAPE and GIA to MSc Energy Courses in gEneSys Countries

The SHAPE and GIA coding exercise was conducted to provide an indicative mapping of how gender and interdisciplinarity are currently integrated into a sample of MSc-level energy education across the four EU countries involved in the gEneSys project. This work addresses longstanding concerns regarding the underrepresentation of women and the limited inclusion of socially engaged perspectives within postgraduate energy programmes (Marshall, 2017; Mahajan & Bandyopadhyay, 2021; Mininni, 2022). Given that the MSc level plays a pivotal role in shaping students' technical specialisations and professional identities, it is useful to understand the orientation and framing of these programmes (Musango & Bassi, 2021; Standal et al., 2020). The exercise aimed at generating a cross-national snapshot of MSc programmes with energy content, highlighting current course designs, disciplinary boundaries, and inclusivity. This approach aligns with the broader objective of fostering gender-just and socially responsive energy transitions, where education systems engage with diverse knowledge frameworks and equip future professionals with both technical expertise and socio-political competencies essential for contemporary energy challenges (Mohr, 2021; Ryser, 2019).

Each gEneSys country partner enrolled in the task was asked to sample MSc programmes with energy content. However, it is important to highlight that none of the samples are meant to be representative of their country in any manner whatsoever (i.e., statistically or otherwise). Rather, the samples are simply meant to provide a glimpse of current programmes and the institutional settings in which they are offered. The samples are, therefore, only illustrative of themselves. The sampling strategy involved selecting MSc programmes with energy content identifiable in their titles, using public university websites and online course catalogues. This selection included courses containing keywords such as energy systems, renewable energy, energy transition, and sustainability, to ensure some degree of cross-country comparability while accommodating national variation in HE.

The courses were coded across four key components: course title, hosting department or faculty, course or module overview, and entry requirements. Each component was categorised into one of three knowledge domains: STEM, SSH, or Interdisciplinary. This categorisation allowed the analysis to capture not only the disciplinary intent but also the institutional framing and the implied audience of each programme. Entry requirements proved particularly revealing for inclusion, as programmes restricting entry to narrowly defined technical backgrounds tended to limit accessibility, while those open to SSH or interdisciplinary entrants signalled broader and more diverse pathways into energy education. To deepen the analysis, SHAPE thematic keywords were

applied to assess whether programmes addressed critical socio-technical and governance issues such as energy justice, engagement, policy, and sustainability practices. Concurrently, GIA lettered methodologies (A–K) were employed to evaluate the extent to which gender and intersectionality were embedded within the curriculum, research priorities, and institutional design. Together, these frameworks facilitated a systematic coding of programmes that accounted not only for disciplinary classification but also for substantive engagement with equity, inclusiveness, and the wider societal dimensions of energy transitions.

While the exercise offers important insights, it is important to note its limitations. For instance, it does not evaluate pedagogical quality or the lived experiences of students and instructors. Instead, it offers a surface-level but methodologically grounded view of programme orientation, based on publicly available materials. Nevertheless, this heuristic approach proved valuable in identifying patterns in how MSc energy programmes are conceived and to whom they are targeted. For example, courses embedded within STEM departments with exclusive technical prerequisites are seemingly less likely to attract SSH-trained or female students. By contrast, interdisciplinary programmes incorporating SHAPE themes and inclusive entry routes demonstrate greater potential for fostering diverse participation. The results for each country are introduced next, in turn.

5.1.1 SHAPE/GIA Analysis of MSc on Energy in Italy

Italy's sample of MSc energy curriculum content is heavily grounded in STEM disciplines, particularly engineering, as can be seen in Table 3 which summarises the results of the exercise. Among the eleven MSc energy courses reviewed in the Italian sample, only five were coded as interdisciplinary. These programmes typically offered elective or supplementary modules on sustainability, environmental management, or energy systems governance. While this indicates some movement toward broader integration, the scope remains limited and often superficial. SHAPE keyword analysis revealed recurring themes such as energy policy, energy governance, energy futures, and low-carbon energy, reflecting a modest engagement with social and policy dimensions of energy systems. However, these themes were often secondary within curricula, lacking sustained or systematic incorporation of social science perspectives.

Gender considerations were notably absent in the Italian sample. None of the programmes explicitly addressed sex, gender, or diversity within their structure or objectives, and consequently, none of the eleven GIA methodological codes (A–K) could be applied. This gap is significant given the increasing emphasis on gender equality within European research and innovation policies. The absence of gender integration highlights a critical limitation in the design and content of the sampled programmes.

While a few courses could potentially provide platforms for integrating gender-sensitive approaches, particularly those focused on sustainability or energy transition, these opportunities were unrealised. Interdisciplinary labels were often applied without extending the ethos to confront gender disparities or to promote inclusivity in student recruitment, pedagogy, or learning outcomes. There was no evident engagement with GIA strategies such as rethinking research priorities, analysing sex, or applying intersectional frameworks, which may be needed for transformative educational reform.

Table 3 Analysis of MSc Energy Courses: Italy

No	Course Name	Course Name	Department University	Course Overview	Entry Requirements	INTER	SHAPE Code	Gender Inclusion
1	Electrical Engineering	STEM	STEM	STEM	STEM	No		No
2	Energy Engineering	STEM	STEM	STEM	STEM	No		No
3	Engineering for the Energy Transition	INTER	INTER	INTER	STEM	Yes	6,10, 18, 7	No
4	Energy Engineering	STEM	STEM	STEM	STEM	No		No
5	Management for Energy and Environmental Transition	INTER	INTER	INTER	SSH	No		No
6	Energy and Nuclear Engineering	STEM	STEM	STEM	STEM	No		No
7	Energy Engineering	STEM	STEM	STEM	STEM	No		No
8	Green Industrial Engineering	INTER	INTER	INTER	STEM	Yes	6, 5, 12	No
9	Electrical Power and Systems Engineering	STEM	STEM	INTER	STEM	Yes	5, 13, 19	No
10	Energy Engineering (Renewables and Environmental Sustainability)	INTER	STEM	INTER	STEM	Yes	5, 6, 18	No
11	Energy and Climate	INTER	INTER	INTER	STEM	No		No

Source: MSc Courses Sampling by gEneSys partners in Italy (2025); Key: INTER= Interdisciplinary

Overall, the Italian sample of MSc energy courses demonstrates a predominance of STEM content with limited interdisciplinary breadth and an absence of gender-focused content. These findings reveal structural gaps in how gender and social dimensions are integrated within the sample curricula. The sampled programmes reflect an early stage in addressing the complex socio-technical challenges of energy transitions and underscore the need for systematic incorporation of social science and gender analysis within the educational framework.

5.1.2 SHAPE/GIA Analys of MSc on Energy in Germany

As can be seen in Table 4 Germany's sample of MSc energy programmes, reflect a relatively balanced combination of STEM and interdisciplinary orientations, with institutions actively attempting to bridge technical expertise and socio-environmental concerns. Among the ten MSc energy courses reviewed in the German sample, five are clearly STEM-focused while the remaining five present themselves as interdisciplinary in both title and approach. This dual emphasis is supported by institutional arrangements facilitating collaboration across departments, including faculties of mechanical, civil, and environmental engineering alongside those specialising in sustainability, planning, and policy. However, entry requirements remain predominantly STEM-based, indicating that technical competence is still regarded as a key prerequisite for admission.

A prominent feature of the sampled German programmes is the considerable integration of SHAPE themes. All ten courses were coded as interdisciplinary in content, with substantive engagement with SHAPE keywords such as energy policy, energy efficiency, low-carbon energy, and energy governance. Some programmes also incorporated less common themes, including energy justice, energy social science, and smart technologies. Notably, these SHAPE elements were embedded within core curricula rather than confined to elective modules, reflecting an emphasis on the societal, political, and cultural aspects that influence the energy transition.

Within this sample, several programmes include modules on sustainable innovation, environmental policy, and systems thinking that expose students to cross-sectoral governance and behavioural change. Certain course tracks are designed to address the management of complex socio-technical systems. This indicates that within the sample, there is a recognition of the importance of interdisciplinary knowledge in tackling the multifaceted challenges of energy transitions.

Gender considerations, while not widespread, are visible in the sample. Two programmes explicitly engage with gender and diversity issues; one includes a mandatory module titled "Expanding Engineering Limits: Culture, Gender, Diversity," which applies GIA methodologies such as rethinking concepts, analysing sex, and intersectional approaches. Another programme integrates gender through compulsory electives, suggesting initial efforts toward mainstreaming gender-responsive pedagogy. Nevertheless, the broader and more systematic application of GIA methodologies, particularly those concerning the interaction of sex and gender, innovation processes, and education design, remains limited within this group of courses.

Table 4 Analysis of MSc Energy Courses: Germany

No	Course Name	Course Name	Department University	Course Overview	Entry Requirements	INTER	SHAPE Code	Gender Inclusion	GIA
1	Nachhaltige Energietechnik	STEM	STEM	STEM	STEM	Yes	5, 10	No	
2	Sustainable Management (Water and Energy)	INTER	INTER	INTER	STEM	Yes	7, 12, 10	Yes	B, D, G
3	Energietechnik	STEM	STEM	STEM	STEM	Yes	15, 9	No	
4	Energy Science and Engineering	STEM	STEM	INTER	STEM	Yes	18, 19, 6	No	
5	Regenerative Energien	INTER	INTER	INTER	STEM	Yes	16, 4, 17	No	
6	Energie- und Verfahrenstechnik	STEM	STEM	STEM	STEM	Yes	6, 15	No	
7	Energie- und Automatisierungssysteme	STEM	STEM	INTER	STEM	Yes	13, 19	No	
8	Clean Energy Processes	INTER	INTER	INTER	STEM	Yes	5, 6, 12	No	
9	Regenerative Energiesysteme	INTER	INTER	INTER	STEM	Yes	8, 17, 7	Yes	D, F, G
10	Chemie - Energie - Umwelt	INTER	INTER	INTER	STEM	Yes	10, 6	No	

Source: MSc Courses Sampling by gEneSys partners in Germany (2025); Key: INTER= Interdisciplinary

Overall, the German sample of MSc energy courses exhibits a balanced mix of STEM-focused and interdisciplinary programmes, with notable integration of SHAPE themes throughout core curricula. While this reflects meaningful engagement with the socio-political and cultural dimensions of energy transitions, gender considerations remain limited and are only explicitly addressed in a small number of courses. The sample reveals initial but incomplete efforts to mainstream gender-responsive pedagogy and intersectional analysis. These findings indicate that although interdisciplinary content is relatively well embedded, further systematic incorporation of GIA methodologies is required to fully address gender and diversity within energy education.

5.1.3 SHAPE/GIA Analys of MSc on Energy in Poland

gEneSys partners in Poland adopted a different approach from the other partners and sampled MSc courses with energy content from their within own institution (one institute within a major University in Poland), introducing an interesting contrast to the analysis. Their choice illustrates a deliberate effort at incorporating gender issues into energy education, largely stemming from the participation of one of their members in the SHAPE project. The selected courses are shown in Table 5. Among the six MSc energy courses reviewed in the Polish sample, three were primarily classified within SSH, while the other three demonstrated interdisciplinary orientations. None of the courses were categorised as purely STEM-based. The programmes covered diverse thematic areas related to energy, indicating an engagement with multiple facets of the energy transition.

The sample revealed widespread inclusion of SHAPE themes across the programmes. Five out of six courses were coded as interdisciplinary based on curricular content, and all incorporated SHAPE keywords such as energy governance, energy poverty, energy practice(s), and energy social science. These themes appeared integrated within course materials, particularly in those focusing on socio-technical systems and spatial transitions. Several programmes employed systems thinking approaches, combining social theoretical insights with practical knowledge related to energy behaviour, policy, and community action.

Critical and justice-oriented SHAPE concepts were also present in the sample. Themes including energy engagement, energy cultures, and energy justice were identified within the courses, although the extent to which they are central to pedagogical goals or embedded across curricula cannot be definitively established from the available data. Some programmes, particularly those linked to humanities and planning disciplines, showed attention to issues of equity, participation, and democratic governance in energy transitions, indicating a degree of social embedding in the educational content.

Regarding gender and diversity, three of the six programmes included content related to gender, intersectionality, and diversity, often within compulsory or foundational modules. These courses activated GIA codes including rethinking concepts and theories (B), analysing sex (D), analysing how sex and gender interact (F), and intersectional approaches (G). The deliberate effort by gEneSys partners involved in the design and teaching of MSc modules with energy content to address inclusion and equity is seen to represent a departure from current practices in the Polish context, where STEM tends to dominate MSc programmes. Thus, the findings from Poland illustrate evolving efforts to incorporate interdisciplinarity and social justice concerns into energy education.

Table 5 Analysis of MSc Energy Courses: Poland

No	Course Name	Course Name	Department University	Course Overview	Entry Requirements	INTER	SHAPE Code	Gender Inclusion	GIA
1	Social aspects of energy production	SSH	STEM	SSH	STEM	No		No	
2	Energy and Environment	INTER	STEM	INTER	STEM	Yes	12, 7, 5	No	
3	Bridging STEM and SSH	INTER	SSH	INTER	SSH	Yes	14, 2, 4	Yes	B, D, F, G
4	Social aspects of Technology	SSH	SSH	INTER	SSH	Yes	17, 8, 14	Yes	B, D, F, G
5	Spatial and Social transitions	SSH	SSH	INTER	SSH	Yes	9, 8, 7	Yes	B, D, F, G
6	Energy systems	INTER	STEM	INTER	STEM	Yes	2, 14	No	

Source: MSc Courses Sampling by gEneSys partners in Poland (2025); Key: INTER= Interdisciplinary

5.1.4 GIA Analys of MSc on Energy in the UK

The sample of MSc energy programmes from the United Kingdom exhibit a broadly interdisciplinary character, with a pronounced emphasis on linking technical expertise with policy, sustainability, and enterprise, as shown in Table 6. Among the ten MSc energy courses reviewed in the UK sample, three were classified as purely STEM based on their titles and departmental affiliations. Most programmes (seven) explicitly articulated interdisciplinary aims, often reflected in their titles and organisational structures, which combine energy with themes such as climate change, management, and policy. Examples include courses titled Renewable Energy, Enterprise and Management, and Humanitarian Engineering with Sustainability, indicating an institutional recognition of the multifaceted nature of the energy transition. Curricular design and learning outcomes, even within engineering faculties, frequently emphasise holistic problem-solving and systems thinking.

The interdisciplinary orientation within the sample is further evident in the flexibility of entry requirements. Although most programmes preferred applicants from STEM backgrounds, several actively encouraged candidates from economics, political science, and environmental policy, particularly for courses with a business or policy focus. This approach broadens accessibility and diversifies the academic cohort, potentially enriching the learning experience. Such openness suggests a capacity within the sampled programmes to prepare graduates capable of navigating the social, economic, and technical complexities of sustainable energy systems.

The UK sample demonstrated strong integration of SHAPE themes, with all ten courses embedding multiple SHAPE keywords across core modules, capstone projects, or interdisciplinary pathways. Frequently observed themes included energy policy, low-carbon energy, energy governance, energy futures, and smart technologies. Additionally, more critical and participatory concepts such as energy justice, energy consumer, and energy engagement were present, often linked to practical activities such as stakeholder mapping and participatory energy planning. This indicates curricula designed not only to teach systems thinking but also to foster civic responsibility and ethical awareness.

Despite the evident curricular breadth and interdisciplinarity, the sample revealed a notable absence of gender and diversity integration according to GIA criteria. None of the courses included gender-sensitive content or methodologies that met the GIA coding framework. This gap highlights an important omission within these otherwise socially engaged programmes. While the UK sample models advanced interdisciplinarity and policy responsiveness, it also underscores the need to embed gender and intersectionality more explicitly. Incorporating these dimensions would enhance educational equity and equip graduates with the critical awareness necessary for leading inclusive and just energy transitions.

Table 6 Analysis of MSc Energy Courses: the UK

No	Course Name	Course Name	Department University	Course Overview	Entry Requirements	INTER	SHAPE Code	Gender Inclusion
1	MSc Sustainable Energy Futures	INTER	STEM	INTER	STEM	Yes	1, 10, 9	No
2	MSc Renewable Energy	STEM	INTER	STEM	STEM	Yes	17	No
3	MSc Renewable Energy and Clean Technology	INTER	STEM	INTER	STEM	Yes	15, 19, 18	No
4	MSc Energy and Environmental Engineering	STEM	STEM	INTER	STEM	Yes	9, 5	No
5	MSc Energy and Climate Policy	INTER	SSH	INTER	INTER	Yes	10, 8, 7	No
6	MSc Sustainable Energy Engineering	STEM	STEM	STEM	STEM	Yes	5, 14	No
7	MSc Energy Policy	INTER	SSH	INTER	INTER	Yes	10, 8, 7	No
8	MSc Renewable Energy, Enterprise and Management (REEM)	INTER	INTER	INTER	STEM	Yes	17, 1	No
9	MSc Humanitarian Engineering with Sustainability	INTER	INTER	INTER	INTER	Yes	12, 4, 14	No
10	MSc Energy Systems and Data Analytics (ESDA)	INTER	STEM	INTER	STEM	Yes	9, 15, 19	No

Source: MSc Courses Sampling by gEneSys partners in the UK (2025); Key: INTER= Interdisciplinary

Gender and Interdisciplinarity in MSc Energy Education: Insights from gEneSys countries

Across the samples from the four countries, interdisciplinarity has emerged as a defining feature of MSc energy programmes, as can be seen on Table 7, though the extent of its depth, institutionalisation, and pedagogical implementation varies considerably. The samples from Germany and the UK display the most consistent and structured approaches, offering programmes where technical competencies are explicitly linked to sustainability, policy, business, and governance. These courses are framed within systems-thinking paradigms that integrate STEM and SSH, which suggest a commitment to prepare students for the complexities inherent in energy transitions. In contrast, Italy's sample remains predominantly embedded within engineering faculties with a strong STEM identity and only limited signs of interdisciplinary content. Poland presents a different profile, with SSH and interdisciplinary approaches much more prominent, being grounded in social theory, planning, and governance, by design. The findings from these samples suggest diverse conceptualisations of the role of disciplinary perspectives in energy education, highlighting that such framing may enable or constrain broader participation.

Despite the increasing adoption of interdisciplinarity, gender integration remains largely absent from the samples of the MSc courses reviewed. Neither Italy nor the UK samples showed evidence of structured gender content or application of GIA. Although the sampled UK programmes demonstrate a prominent interdisciplinary curricula, they consistently lack meaningful engagement with gender, equity, or intersectionality. The sample from Germany performs slightly better, with two courses explicitly addressing gender, cultural sensitivity, and diversity, enabling application of GIA B, D, and G. By contrast, the three SSH-oriented programmes in the sample from Poland include gender-related content, by design. However, gender themes appear sporadically in the samples from Germany and Poland, rather than as a consistent element across curricula. This suggests a disconnect between interdisciplinarity and gender-sensitive pedagogies that may limit the inclusivity of energy education.

Interdisciplinarity offers a potential pathway to broaden participation in MSc energy programmes, particularly for women and students from non-technical backgrounds. Programmes that bridge STEM and SSH domains tend to provide more accessible and socially relevant entry points. Examples include Humanitarian Engineering with Sustainability in the UK and Social Aspects of Energy Production in Poland, which address ethical, political, and community dimensions of energy. These approaches could help mitigate persistent gender imbalances. However, without the explicit incorporation of gender in curriculum design, messaging, and teaching methods, opportunities to advance gender equity in energy education are likely to remain neglected.

For interdisciplinarity to contribute effectively to inclusive energy education, it should be embedded within intentional institutional strategies that prioritise equity throughout course development and delivery. This requires rethinking knowledge framing, assessment, and communication. The GIA methodologies provide concrete tools for such work, including GIA A, G, and J. Yet these methodologies remain underutilised in the sampled MSc courses. Systematic integration of GIA could support institutions in diversifying participation and transforming epistemological approaches to energy education, enhancing both social relevance and equity.

Report on Gender Perspectives into EUA Recommendations on Energy R&I and Education

Table 7 Analys of MSc Energy Courses in gEneSys Countries

Country	Course No.	Course Name	Department University	Course Overview	Entry Requirements	INTER	SHAPE Codes	Gender Inclusion	GIA Codes
Italy	11	INTER (5)	INTER (3)	STEM (5) INTER (6)	STEM (10) SSH (1)	No (7) Yes (4)	5, 6, 7, 10, 12, 13, 18, 19	No	None
Germany	10	STEM (5) INTER (5)	STEM (5) INTER (5)	STEM (3) INTER (7)	STEM (10)	Yes (10)	4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 12, 13, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19	No (8) Yes (2)	B, D, F, G
Poland	6	SSH (3) INTER (3)	STEM (2) INTER (1) SSH (3)	SSH (1) INTER (5)	STEM (2) SSH (4)	Yes (6)	2, 4, 5, 7, 8, 9, 12, 14, 17	No (3) Yes (3)	B, D, F, G
UK	10	STEM (3) INTER (7)	STEM (5) SSH (1) INTER (3)	STEM (2) INTER (8)	STEM (7) INTER (3)	Yes (10)	1, 4, 5, 7, 8, 9, 10, 12, 14, 15, 17, 18, 19	No (10)	None

Source: Compiled from MSc Sampling by gEneSys partners in Italy, Germany, Poland, and the UK (2025)

6. ORIGINS, AIMS, AND STRATEGIC CONTEXT OF THE 2017 EUA ENERGY TRANSITION AGENDA

The 2017 EUA document on Energy Transition Research and Innovation emerged from a growing recognition of the central role that universities must play in addressing the complex challenges of the global energy transition. As Europe faces the dual imperative of decarbonising its energy systems while maintaining economic competitiveness and social cohesion, the EUA highlights the importance of HE institutions as hubs for knowledge production, innovation, and education. The report positions universities not only as centres of technological development but also as spaces for generating inclusive and holistic solutions. Its mission is to equip universities to lead in sustainability transitions by supporting interdisciplinary research, fostering innovation ecosystems, and educating professionals who are capable of navigating complex socio-technical systems (EUA, 2017).

A cornerstone of the EUA's vision is the dismantling of disciplinary silos, with a strong emphasis on collaboration across engineering, natural sciences, social sciences, and the humanities. The aim is to cultivate a more integrated academic environment where solutions to energy challenges reflect both technological and societal dimensions. The EUA encourages institutional strategies that facilitate this cross-disciplinary approach through curriculum design, joint research agendas, and intersectoral partnerships. The development of such strategies is seen as crucial for building the capacities and mindsets necessary to address the multifaceted nature of the energy transition (EUA, 2017). The EUA notes challenges and opportunities for three technologically important areas for future ERIE. These are shown in Table 8 which summarises some of these challenges.

Table 8 EUA Challenges and Opportunities for Future ERIE

Strand	Addressing Challenges and Opportunities
Energy Efficiency	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ develop and design new energy efficient technologies and materials while simultaneously developing a strategy for getting them to be accepted on the market ➤ make master's teaching energy efficiency a core topic in curriculum involving energy technologies and/or the socioeconomic aspects of energy ➤ ensure that energy efficiency issues are integral to any master's programme for students wishing to plan and operate industrial sites and/or buildings ➤ ensure that all doctoral candidates in energy-relevant disciplines develop a fundamental understanding of social and behavioural aspects of energy efficiency
Smart Grid and Systems	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ find better ways to match generation with consumption, especially as renewable-based generation is available intermittently, uncontrollable and therefore unable to track demand ➤ move towards carbon-neutral energy generation that matches demand ➤ understand that energy has a very strong social aspect, involving building energy communities to support decentralisation, while instilling responsibility about consumption and teaching awareness of the socio-economic impact of decisions such as demand driven response (e.g., avoid detrimental effects such as enlarging the gap between rich and poor) ➤ understand that policy can have a particularly important influence on technological development and integration (e.g., Photo-Voltaic technology) ➤ understand the ethical implications of integrating technologies (e.g., smart metering) and impacts on user behaviour, especially when this results in pricing changes and could drive more people into fuel poverty

Report on Gender Perspectives into EUA Recommendations on Energy R&I and Education

Renewable Energy Integration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ fully and effectively integrate RE technologies in a way that maximises their contribution to meeting our energy needs ➤ recognise that society tends to consider energy services as more desirable than energy itself (e.g., the social value of what energy can achieve is higher than its intrinsic value); energy as a demand that needs to be met using renewable energy to minimise environmental impact ➤ understand how different forms of energy are used and their respective value to society ➤ any energy related master's programme must consider the economic, social and political factors influencing energy; need to consider the role of society and citizens
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Source: EUA (2017)

The EUA recommendations align closely with broader European policy frameworks, most notably the Strategic Energy Technology Plan (SET-Plan). The SET-Plan is the EU's flagship strategy to accelerate the development and deployment of low-carbon technologies through coordinated research and innovation (EC, 2025). The EUA complements this policy landscape by underscoring the importance of universities in providing the skilled workforce and multidisciplinary research needed to meet SET-Plan goals. It highlights the potential of academic institutions to act as bridges between government, industry, and civil society, fostering socially accepted, economically viable energy innovations across the continent.

The Action Agenda proposed in the 2017 EUA document delineates a comprehensive strategy for European universities to actively contribute to the continent's energy transition. Structured around four key strands (General, Energy Efficiency, Smart and Grid Systems, Renewable Energy Integration), the agenda underscores the need for interdisciplinary collaboration, integrating both STEM and SSH disciplines, to address the multifaceted challenges of energy transitions. The General strand advocates for the integration of social sciences and humanities with technological sciences to solve complex energy problems, emphasising the development of new educational profiles such as Energy System Scientists and Energy Economists. The Energy Efficiency strand focuses on removing non-technical barriers, promoting behavioural insights, and enhancing policy frameworks to improve energy consumption patterns. The Smart and Grid Systems strand highlights the importance of training on effectively communicating smart meter usage to end-users, ensuring that technological advancements are accessible and understandable to the public. The Renewable Energy Integration strand calls for involving residents and citizens through participatory activities and events, fostering community engagement and acceptance of renewable energy projects. Collectively, these recommendations aim to position universities as pivotal actors in driving sustainable, inclusive, and socially responsive energy transitions across Europe (EUA, 2017). The EUA recommendations themselves are components of the Action Agenda, set out in Appendix D (EUA, 2017: 50-53). Table 9 illustrates the themes and number of recommendations in each theme.

Table 9 EUA ERIE Recommendations by Strand

Strand	No of Recommendations
General	31
Energy Efficiency	14
Smart Grids and Systems	12
Renewable Energy Integration	7

6.1 SHAPE AND GIA INTO EUA ERIE RECOMMENDATIONS

A central argument is that SHAPE and GIA provide complementary and effective tools for analysing and enhancing the social dimensions of ERIE. These frameworks are especially relevant for evaluating the EUA's 2017 recommendations, which emphasise interdisciplinary collaboration and societal impact but address gender and intersectionality only marginally. SHAPE focuses on the role of social sciences, humanities, and the arts in energy transitions, offering 20 keywords that help assess how EUA strategies engage with complex social dynamics such as energy justice, culture, citizenship, and governance. This enhances the recommendations' sensitivity to human behaviours and societal contexts influencing energy systems. Meanwhile, GIA provides a structured methodological approach to embedding gender and intersectional analysis in research and teaching, addressing common gender blindness in STEM fields. It highlights the importance of recognising multiple social identities in shaping energy access and innovation. When applied to EUA recommendations, GIA identifies gaps in inclusivity and suggests evidence-based strategies to promote equity, making energy transitions not only innovative and efficient but also socially just.

Evidence from a range of studies highlights the value of integrating SHAPE and GIA frameworks in energy education and innovation. Kowalska et al. (2022) demonstrate how gender differences in household energy behaviours in Poland underscore the need for SHAPE concepts such as energy culture and energy behaviour. Similarly, Maier et al. (2019) identify persistent gender barriers in engineering education in Germany, advocating for intersectional analysis aligned with GIA methodologies. These cases illustrate that without frameworks such as SHAPE and GIA, gender and social dimensions remain marginalised in energy education, limiting the effectiveness and reach of innovation efforts. Incorporating these approaches into EUA policy analysis can make gender and interdisciplinarity more visible, actionable, and embedded institutionally.

Further examples from diverse regions reinforce this integrated need. Ramisio et al. (2021) report that European energy innovation systems often lack gender-sensitive metrics and fail to address structural inequalities, pointing to the role of GIA's intersectional and institutional reform approaches. Peña et al. (2021) highlight the absence of gender-disaggregated data in Latin American energy education, reflecting the necessity of combining SHAPE's socio-cultural insights with GIA's gender-specific tools for curriculum development and research agendas. In Central and Eastern Europe, Bogovac et al. (2021) document how cultural norms and socio-economic status intersect with gender to exacerbate barriers in STEM education, further supporting the application of GIA. Asian studies by Chen et al. (2015) and Irie and Kawahara (2021) reveal gendered differences in environmental attitudes among students in Taiwan and Japan, underscoring the importance of interdisciplinary pedagogies advocated by SHAPE. Ring et al. (2022) examine Swedish institutional cultures that perpetuate masculine norms, limiting women's participation in energy careers and illustrating the need for GIA-informed institutional reforms.

The transformative potential of combining SHAPE and GIA also lies in addressing justice in energy transitions globally. Ahmer (2021) identifies how cultural and institutional norms in Pakistan contribute to gendered exclusion from renewable energy education, conditions that SHAPE's socio-cultural perspective and GIA's gender analysis jointly illuminate. Rincon-Flores et al. (2020) discuss gendered power dynamics in energy community engagement across Mexico and the U.S., further emphasising the necessity of an integrated SHAPE-GIA approach for equity and empowerment. Pailman and de Groot (2022) find that gender remains marginalised or isolated in

African sustainability curricula, reinforcing the need for comprehensive frameworks. Allen et al. (2019) expose the underrepresentation and lower recognition of women in U.S. energy research publications, showing how institutional reforms supported by GIA and SHAPE are essential to transforming research governance and enabling more diverse knowledge production.

These global findings suggest that the combined SHAPE-GIA framework may provide EUA recommendations and higher education institutions with useful tools to support more inclusive, interdisciplinary, and socially aware energy futures. This integrated approach could potentially enhance participation, equity, and innovation by addressing the complex socio-technical challenges of energy transitions.

6.2 Integrating SHAPE and GIA into EUA ERIE Recommendations

The integration of SHAPE and GIA into the EUA recommendations followed a few steps, as shown in Table 10.

Table 10 Steps for Applying SHAPE and GIA to the EUA Recommendations

1. Analysis of EUA recommendation (number and themes)	2. What SHAPE keywords apply? (number)	3. What GIA methodologies apply? (letters)	4. SHAPE and GIA coding of relevant journal articles from gEneSys SLR	5. Journal Articles that best illustrate the SHAPE/GIA coded recommendation
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Prior to carrying out the SHAPE/GIA coding of the EUA recommendation, it was necessary to analyse and interpret each to capture the key issues involved and the aim and thrust of the recommendation to infer plausible connections with wider issues. This was to ensure that their subsequent coding reflected the aims and intent encapsulated in each recommendation. Table 11 illustrates the analysis of one random recommendation from each of the four strands.

Table 11 Analysis of EUA ERIE Recommendations

No.	General	Analysis of Recommendation for SHAPE and GIA coding
6	Adapt teaching methodologies for future energy professionals, integrating project-based courses with an integrated approach, including teamwork (groups of 3-10 students), visits, and work with companies or municipalities on real-world projects	it calls for experiential, collaborative, and practice-based learning and encourages teaching methods that simulate real-world energy challenges, involving interdisciplinary teamwork, stakeholder interaction, and applied learning environments, aiming at equipping students with the technical, social, and collaborative skills needed for effective engagement in complex, real-world energy systems
No.	Energy Efficiency	Analysis of Recommendation for SHAPE and GIA coding
11	Develop campus energy manager profiles	it refers to creating role definitions and competencies for professionals responsible for overseeing energy sustainability in university campuses; profiles would likely guide hiring, training, and performance standards, ensuring energy managers are equipped to manage technical systems, influence behaviour, and coordinate institutional energy strategies
No.	Smart Grid and Systems	Analysis of Recommendation for SHAPE and GIA coding
5	Establish new master's programmes on how to communicate emerging technologies like smart metering,	it proposes creating educational programmes that equip students with the skills to communicate complex, emerging energy technologies (e.g., smart meters), in a way that is understandable,

	which may have a strong impact on the overall energy system, to end-users	meaningful, and actionable for diverse user groups; it emphasises the interface between technology, society, and communication, aiming to improve user engagement and system transformation through education
No.	<i>Renewable Energy Integration</i>	<i>Analysis of Recommendation for SHAPE and GIA coding</i>
2	Transfer knowledge from oil- and gas-based energy systems to a sustainable approach and use of renewable resources	it focuses on leveraging existing expertise from conventional energy sectors (e.g. fossil fuels) to support the transition to sustainable, renewable energy systems; it acknowledges the importance of continuity, reskilling, and systems thinking, while intimating a shift in knowledge application from carbon-intensive to low-carbon pathways

Source: Analysis by the authors

The next step entailed the use of SHAPE and GIA to systematically analyse the four thematic strands of the EUA’s ERIE. As seen previously, the SHAPE lexicon offers a set of 20 keywords to assess the presence of social science and humanities themes across energy-related recommendations. GIA, by contrast, brings a gender and intersectional lens through its methodologies (A–K). Together, they enable a layered, intersectional analysis of how the EUA recommendations may be enhanced to reflect more inclusive, socially grounded, and gender-responsive innovation strategies.

The rationale for integrating both SHAPE and GIA frameworks lay in their complementarity: SHAPE helped identify the social and cultural relevance of each recommendation, while GIA ensured that gender and diversity concerns were systematically foregrounded. Given the project’s central concern with gender, the GIA code E (Analysing Gender) was applied to all recommendations as a baseline since all recommendations entail social engagement to varying degrees. The number of SHAPE codes per recommendation was capped at three, and GIA codes capped at four (including E) to ensure a best fit between the most relevant keywords and methodologies with the wording, aim and intent of each recommendation, although further SHAPE keywords and GIA letters may well be applicable to lesser degrees. Still, this focus helped provide sufficient detail without obfuscating the analysis, while ensuring that core social and gendered dimensions were thoroughly examined. The combined coding yielded insights into both thematic depth and institutional blind spots in EUA’s otherwise forward-thinking recommendations. Table 12 shows a sample of one EUA recommendation from each strand demonstrating the rationale guiding the coding with SHAPE keywords from the lexicon and the GIA letter-coded methodologies.

Report on Gender Perspectives into EUA Recommendations on Energy R&I and Education

Table 12 Sample of SHAPE/GIA coded EUA Recommendations for Each Strand

No.	General	Rationale for SHAPE and GIA coding	
		SHAPE*	GIA**
6	Adapt teaching methodologies for future energy professionals, integrating project-based courses with an integrated approach, including teamwork (groups of 3-10 students), visits, and work with companies or municipalities on real-world projects	<p>6: emphasis on preparing students for real-world, future-facing energy challenges through hands-on, collaborative learning aligns with envisioning and shaping sustainable energy futures</p> <p>12: Project-based and teamwork-oriented methods simulate professional energy practices, reflecting how energy is co-produced and applied in social contexts</p> <p>14: promotes pedagogies that integrate societal engagement (e.g., with companies and /municipalities), reflecting a social science-informed view of energy as embedded in communities and governance structures.</p>	<p>A: shifts learning priorities from abstract theory to real-world problem solving, preparing students for socially relevant innovation</p> <p>C: encourages students to develop applied research questions in interdisciplinary and practical settings, enhancing the gender and social responsiveness of inquiry</p> <p>E: Inclusive teaching strategies that involve diverse team-based learning may expose or address gender dynamics in collaboration and professional contexts</p> <p>H: Embedding real-world, multi-actor problem solving into pedagogy transforms how engineering is taught, making space for socially responsible innovation practice</p>
No.	Energy Efficiency	Rationale for SHAPE and GIA coding	
11	Develop campus energy manager profiles	<p>7: establishing a formal role such as an energy manager institutionalises governance mechanisms for energy use and sustainability at the campus level</p> <p>12: the energy manager role is inherently practice-based, involving day-to-day operational decisions and stakeholder engagement in managing energy systems</p> <p>16: campus energy managers are key agents in implementing and leading institutional energy transitions, aligning internal practices with broader sustainability goals</p>	<p>A: this role reorients institutional priorities toward operational energy responsibility, linking research, teaching, and administration with sustainability targets</p> <p>B: challenges traditional ideas of energy management by embedding sustainability and potentially gender equity into operational leadership roles</p> <p>E: including gender analysis in designing these profiles can help ensure that hiring, leadership, and decision-making structures are inclusive and not reproducing existing inequalities</p> <p>H: The development of such profiles involves rethinking technical and organisational processes, including how innovative solutions are implemented and by whom</p>
No.	Smart Grid and Systems	Rationale for SHAPE and GIA coding	

5	Establish new master's programmes on how to communicate emerging technologies like smart metering, which may have a strong impact on the overall energy system, to end-users	<p>6: teaching communication of emerging technologies helps shape how societies anticipate and adapt to future energy systems, making this keyword highly relevant</p> <p>14: communicating smart technologies involves understanding user behaviour, perception, and trust, which are core concerns of social science in energy studies</p> <p>17: explicitly promotes engagement with end-users, focusing on communication strategies that foster inclusivity and public understanding</p>	<p>C: a master's programme focused on technology communication invites new lines of inquiry about how gender and social identity shape perceptions of, and responses to, smart technologies</p> <p>E: Communication must consider how different gendered experiences affect access to, and comfort with, technologies such as smart metering</p> <p>F: a deeper understanding of how gender intersects with other identities (e.g., age, class) informs the design of inclusive communication strategies</p> <p>H: teaching communication of smart systems involves rethinking technical innovation as a socio-technical process, incorporating diverse user needs and feedback into design and deployment</p>
No.	Renewable Energy Integration	Rationale for SHAPE and GIA coding	
2	Transfer knowledge from oil- and gas-based energy systems to a sustainable approach and use of renewable resources	<p>7: transitioning knowledge from fossil-based systems to renewables requires institutional and regulatory adaptation, central to governance debates</p> <p>16: enabling a shift from carbon-intensive systems to sustainable, renewable ones</p> <p>18: directly focuses on moving toward low-carbon energy systems, making this keyword especially pertinent</p>	<p>A: calls for a paradigm shift in energy knowledge systems, directing focus away from fossil fuels and toward renewables</p> <p>B: involves revisiting and revising traditional engineering and economic models that were developed for oil and gas contexts</p> <p>E: gendered divisions of labour and expertise in the fossil fuel industry may be reproduced unless actively addressed in knowledge transfer and retraining processes</p> <p>G: recognises that the impacts of fossil fuel dependency and renewable transitions vary across social groups, necessitating inclusive and equitable transition strategies</p>
*Numbered SHAPE Keywords: 6 = Energy future(s); 7= Energy governance; 12= Energy practice(s); 14= Energy social science; 16= Energy transition; 18= Low-carbon energy			
** Lettered GIA Methodologies: A= Rethinking research priorities and outcomes; B= Rethinking concepts and theories; C= Formulating research questions; E= Analysing Gender; F= Analysing how gender and sex interact; G= Intersectional approaches; H= Engineering innovation processes			

Report on Gender Perspectives into EUA Recommendations on Energy R&I and Education

To ground the coding exercise in empirical research, each SHAPE/GIA-coded EUA recommendation was illustrated with journal articles from the gEneSys Systematic Literature Review (SLR) database. (Cellini, 2024) This database was collaboratively compiled by SSH and STEM scholars within the gEneSys consortium during Spring 2023, using the Web of Science to identify studies examining the intersection of gender and energy transitions. The final SLR included 152 articles, with approximately two-thirds (98) published between 2020 and 2023, and the remaining third (54) published from 2005 to 2019. The SLR findings emphasised the significance of intersectionality, showing how gender interacts with other social factors such as race, ethnicity, age, education, and class. For the coding exercise, thematically relevant articles from the SLR were SHAPE/GIA coded to form a pool of about 70 papers, from which the most pertinent were selected to illustrate each EUA recommendation (see Appendix II). A sample of SHAPE/GIA coded and illustrated EUA recommendations from across the four strands is shown in Table 13².

Table 13 Literature Supporting the SHAPE/GIA Coding of EUA Recommendations

No.	General	SHAPE and GIA coding Illustrated by Supporting SLR articles		
		SHAPE*	GIA**	Supporting SLR articles
6	Adapt teaching methodologies for future energy professionals, integrating project-based courses with an integrated approach, including teamwork (groups of 3-10 students), visits, and work with companies or municipalities on real-world projects	6, 12, 14	A, C, E, H	Ryser (2019); Kim et al., (2020); Ahåmer (2021)
No.	Energy Efficiency	SHAPE and GIA coding Illustrated by Supporting SLR articles		
		SHAPE*	GIA**	Supporting SLR articles
11	Develop campus energy manager profiles	7, 12, 16	A, B, E, H	Standal et al. (2020); Ahåmer (2021); Musango & Bassi (2021)
No.	Smart Grid and Systems	SHAPE and GIA coding Illustrated by Supporting SLR articles		
		SHAPE	GIA	
5	Establish new master's programmes on how to communicate emerging technologies like smart metering, which may have a strong impact on the overall energy system, to end-users	6, 14, 17	C, E, F, H	Ryser (2019); Kim et al., (2020); Standal et al., (2020)
No.	Renewable Energy Integration	SHAPE and GIA coding Illustrated by Supporting SLR articles		
		SHAPE	GIA	
2	Transfer knowledge from oil- and gas-based energy systems to a sustainable approach and use of renewable resources	7, 16, 18	A, B, E, G	Ockwell et al. (2018); Mahajan & Bandyopadhyay (2021); Musango & Bassi (2021)

*Numbered SHAPE Keywords: 6 = Energy future(s); 7= Energy governance; 12= Energy practice(s); 14= Energy social science; 16= Energy transition; 18= Low-carbon energy

** Lettered GIA Methodologies: A= Rethinking research priorities and outcomes; B= Rethinking concepts and theories; C= Formulating research questions; E= Analysing Gender; F= Analysing how gender and sex interact; G= Intersectional approaches; H= Engineering innovation processes

Source: Compiled from EUA (2017), SHAPE (2017) and GI (gEneSys, 2024) by gEneSys partners in the UK

² The full set of SHAPE/GIA coded recommendations with supporting literature can be found in Appendix III

6.3 Outcomes for EUA General ERIE Recommendations

The SHAPE and GIA coding of the EUA general recommendations indicates a foundational yet uneven integration of social sciences, humanities, and gender-sensitive approaches within energy education and research. For example, General Recommendation 6, which advocates project-based, collaborative learning grounded in real-world contexts, aligns with SHAPE keywords 6 (energy futures), 12 (energy practices), and 14 (energy social science). Correspondingly, it reflects GIA methodologies A (Rethinking Research Priorities), C (Formulating Research Questions), E (Analysing Gender), and H (Engineering Innovation Processes). Empirical studies from Ryser (2019), Kim et al. (2020), and Ahämer (2021) reinforce this alignment, demonstrating how participatory learning and interdisciplinary teaching foster inclusivity, learner agency, and socio-technical competence in energy education.

More broadly, international research highlights that energy transitions are socio-technical systems influenced by governance structures, social identities, and institutional cultures. The EUA general recommendations implicitly engage SHAPE keywords 7 (energy governance), 17 (energy engagement), and 14 (energy social science), reflecting an increasing recognition that energy education must address societal dynamics alongside technological development. Work by Musango and Bassi (2021), Mininni (2022), and Mohr (2021) illustrates how embedding these dimensions into curricula better prepares graduates to tackle complex energy challenges, moving education beyond narrow technical training.

GIA coding complements SHAPE by explicitly highlighting gender and intersectionality as critical structural components in energy education and research. Codes E (Analysing Gender) and G (Intersectional Approaches) focus attention on the power relations shaping knowledge production and participation in the energy sector. Studies by Musango and Bassi (2021) and Standal et al. (2020) reveal that absent gender-sensitive frameworks, educational institutions risk perpetuating exclusionary practices. Furthermore, GIA codes I (Rethinking Standards and References) and K (Rethinking Language and Visual Representations) challenge prevailing technical discourses that often marginalise diverse perspectives, thereby constraining innovation and inclusivity.

The combined SHAPE and GIA coding highlights the importance of inclusive communication, representational diversity, and participatory pedagogy in transforming how knowledge is created and delivered in higher education. Mohr (2021) and others demonstrate that co-produced knowledge with communities enhances energy citizenship and empowers marginalised groups. When applied through SHAPE and GIA frameworks, the EUA general recommendations gain specificity as actionable strategies, shifting energy education and research from hierarchical and fragmented models towards open, reflexive, and socially engaged approaches. This integrated lens emphasises that technical skills alone are insufficient, and that ethical responsibility, gender justice, and community engagement are essential to cultivating diverse energy professionals ready to lead sustainable transitions.

6.4 Outcomes for EUA ERIE Recommendations on Energy Efficiency

The SHAPE and GIA coding of the Energy Efficiency strand demonstrates how embedding interdisciplinary and gender-responsive approaches can broaden the scope and deepen the impact of EUA guidance. Recommendation 11, which suggests developing campus energy manager profiles, aligns with SHAPE keywords 7 (energy governance), 12 (energy practices), and 16 (energy transition). These codes emphasise the significance of institutional leadership roles that manage energy use while engaging students and staff in cultivating energy cultures. Corresponding GIA codes A (Rethinking Research Priorities), B (Rethinking Concepts and Theories), E (Analysing

Gender), and H (Engineering innovation processes) enhance this recommendation by ensuring these roles consider gender dynamics and challenge traditional notions of technical expertise.

Empirical evidence supporting this coding comes from several studies. Standal et al. (2020) demonstrate how local governance structures can either enable or constrain women's participation in energy decision-making, highlighting the importance of inclusive institutional roles. Ahämer (2021) shows that involving students in practical campus sustainability projects enhances learning outcomes and leadership skills. Additionally, Musango and Bassi (2021) apply systems thinking to reveal how gender-sensitive approaches can transform energy governance practices. These examples underline the value of combining applied practice with critical reflection on power, gender, and inclusion in energy efficiency education.

The literature across the Energy Efficiency strand highlights that technological solutions alone do not ensure equitable outcomes. Research from Poland (Kowalska et al., 2022), the EU (Łapniewska, 2019), South Korea (Kim and Hwang, 2022), and India (Mahajan and Bandyopadhyay, 2021) illustrates how energy-saving behaviours are influenced by gendered norms, household dynamics, and social policies. SHAPE keywords 5 (energy efficiency), 1 (energy behaviour), and 14 (energy social science) capture the socio-cultural contexts shaping energy use and the uptake of efficiency measures. These findings highlight the importance of educating students about the behavioural, cultural, and institutional factors affecting energy consumption.

GIA methodologies further elucidate how social structures and inequalities influence energy efficiency. Codes such as E (Analysing Gender), F (How Sex and Gender Interact), and G (Intersectional Approaches) point to disparities in access to energy knowledge, resources, and decision-making power across gender and other identity markers. Kowalska et al. (2022) emphasise women's roles in household energy management, while Łapniewska (2019) critiques EU policies for overlooking these contributions. Kim and Hwang (2022) demonstrate that culturally responsive policies achieve greater uptake when aligned with local gender roles. Inclusion of GIA codes I (Rethinking Standards and References) and J (Rethinking Language and Visual representations) indicates a shift towards more inclusive metrics and discourses. Conventional technocratic models often marginalise women's experiential knowledge. The literature advocates for participatory, community-driven approaches that enhance both efficiency and democratic engagement. By integrating SHAPE and GIA, EUA's recommendations support an energy efficiency agenda that connects technical performance with equity, empowerment, and inclusive pedagogy.

6.5 Outcomes for EUA ERIE Recommendations on Smart and Grid Systems

The SHAPE and GIA coding of the Smart and Grid Systems strand highlights the increasing need to integrate public engagement, communication, and gender-responsive education within highly technical fields. Recommendation 5, which advocates for new master's programmes focused on communicating emerging technologies such as smart metering to end-users, addresses the necessity of embedding technological innovation within social contexts. This aligns with SHAPE keywords 6 (energy futures), 14 (energy social science), and 17 (energy engagement), emphasising curricula that link technical knowledge with societal realities. Complementary GIA codes C (Formulating Research Questions), E (Analysing Gender), F (Analysing How Sex and Gender interact), and H (Engineering Innovation Processes) ensure gendered and intersectional considerations are integrated into educational content and design.

Empirical studies support these coding choices. Ryser (2019) shows that culturally sensitive, inclusive communication is crucial for marginalised groups, especially women, to engage with smart technologies effectively. Kim et al. (2020) demonstrate how interdisciplinary, user-centred education enhances both learner outcomes and technology uptake by foregrounding equity in design. Standal et al. (2020) provide evidence from the UK and Norway illustrating how social identities influence the usability and acceptance of smart grid innovations, reinforcing the importance of bridging technical and social knowledge in curricula. Together, these studies affirm the relevance of Recommendation 5 in cultivating equitable, communication-competent professionals for smart energy systems.

Beyond curriculum, the coding draws attention to the social structures influencing technology deployment. Research from Nigeria (John et al., 2018), South Africa (Musango and Bassi, 2021), India (Mahajan and Bandyopadhyay, 2021), and Morocco (Ryser, 2019) shows that without context-sensitive planning, innovations such as smart grids and energy storage risk perpetuating existing social inequalities. SHAPE keywords 9 (energy models), 15 (energy storage), and 17 (energy engagement) reflect the systemic dimensions of these technologies. GIA methodologies H (rethinking innovation processes), K (rethinking language and visual representations), and G (intersectional approaches) offer practical tools to ensure inclusive and equitable adoption.

The evidence cautions that neglecting social frameworks may marginalise vulnerable groups. Ryser's (2019) findings from Morocco highlight how gender norms and limited tailored communication restrict women's participation in energy transitions. John et al. (2018) identify gender disparities in youth-led smart energy entrepreneurship, calling for systemic reforms to enhance inclusion. Musango and Bassi (2021) demonstrate the necessity of embedding intersectionality into smart grid planning to prevent reinforcing exclusion. These studies underscore the importance of reflexive research and curriculum design advocated by the coding, urging institutions to prioritise inclusion in both education and technological innovation. This integrated approach equips future professionals with the socio-technical fluency essential for leading equitable, participatory energy transitions and strengthens the societal relevance of smart energy systems.

6.5 Outcomes for EUA Recommendations on Renewable Energy Integration

The SHAPE and GIA coding of the Renewable Energy Integration strand highlights the need to conceptualise energy transitions not merely as technical challenges but as socially embedded processes involving equity, inclusion, and institutional transformation. Recommendation 2, which advocates transferring knowledge from oil- and gas-based systems to renewable energy approaches, aligns with SHAPE keywords 7 (energy governance), 16 (energy transition), and 18 (low-carbon energy). These codes reflect the multifaceted nature of renewable transitions requiring policy reforms, institutional realignments, and curricular changes. Complementary GIA codes A (Rethinking research priorities), B (Rethinking concepts and theories), E (Analysing gender), and G (Intersectional Approaches) emphasise the need to challenge dominant disciplinary paradigms and address structural inequalities within the sector.

This coding is supported by research such as Ockwell et al. (2018), who stress the importance of inclusive innovation systems and capacity-building in the Global South, urging energy education and research to disrupt inherited knowledge hierarchies. Mahajan and Bandyopadhyay (2021) provide evidence from India showing that women in renewable energy frequently encounter barriers stemming from male-dominated fossil fuel sectors. Musango and Bassi (2021), working in South Africa, advocate integrating gender into systems thinking to develop more inclusive models of energy governance. These studies reinforce the SHAPE and GIA coding by underlining the

significance of embedding gender and intersectionality in restructuring energy systems and educational frameworks.

The strand also emphasises justice-oriented approaches in education and governance. SHAPE keywords 7 (energy governance), 16 (energy transition), and 17 (energy engagement) reflect the importance of participatory frameworks that extend beyond technical solutions to address the lived realities of marginalised communities. GIA codes E (Analysing gender), G (Intersectional Approaches), and I (Rethinking Standards) highlight how energy education and policy risk perpetuating exclusion unless inclusive language, representation, and standards are adopted. Research from Africa and India consistently demonstrates that gender norms, class, and geography intersect to influence access to knowledge, leadership, and infrastructure, raising the imperative for inclusive educational practices and institutional reform.

This coding further underscores the value of participatory governance and community-based learning in fostering equitable energy transitions. Ockwell et al. (2018) and Musango and Bassi (2021) illustrate how stakeholder inclusion in energy planning improves outcomes, legitimacy, and trust. Mahajan and Bandyopadhyay (2021) and Mininni (2022) show that women’s active participation in renewable energy systems is crucial for local adoption and long-term success but is often obstructed by institutional inertia. Embedding GIA methodologies such as A (Rethinking Research Priorities) and B (Rethinking Concepts and Theories) in EUA guidance could help challenge these institutional barriers and support the development of socially grounded, technically robust energy strategies. Overall, this strand exemplifies how SHAPE and GIA frameworks can reinforce the social dimensions of energy education by transforming technical knowledge transfer into a vehicle for inclusive, systemic change.

6.7 Synthesising the EUA ERIE Recommendations through the Lens of GIA

The four thematic strands of the EUA ERIE recommendations each address distinct focal areas yet collectively underscore the significance of embedding gender and intersectionality to enhance the relevance, equity, and societal impact of energy education and research. GIA methodologies E (Analysing Gender) and G (Intersectional Approaches) are crucial for uncovering institutional blind spots, challenging normative assumptions, and enriching research design and implementation. For example, the General ERIE strand highlights how male-dominated cultures and leadership limit inclusivity, while the Energy Efficiency and Smart Systems strands expose risks of technical innovation reinforcing existing social hierarchies. The GIA framework clarifies that effective energy transitions require dismantling exclusionary structures alongside technological advancement.

Within the Energy Efficiency strand, GIA codes F (Rethinking How Sex and Gender Interact), I (Rethinking Standards and References), and J (Rethinking Language and Visual Representations) are particularly salient. Traditional efficiency programmes often overlook gendered household roles and social dynamics that shape energy use and access. Empirical studies from Poland (Kowalska et al., 2022), South Korea (Kim & Hwang, 2022), and India (Mahajan & Bandyopadhyay, 2021) reveal women’s central but frequently unacknowledged roles in household energy decisions. Incorporating intersectional insights into both education and policy, as reflected in the EUA recommendations, can foster more equitable and effective energy efficiency strategies by connecting technical measures with socio-cultural realities.

The Smart and Grid Systems strand, where technological complexity predominates, benefits from GIA methodologies H (Rethinking Innovation Processes) and K (Rethinking Language and Visual Representations). Studies from Morocco (Ryser, 2019), Nigeria (John et al., 2018), and South Africa (Musango & Bassi, 2021) demonstrate how smart technologies may perpetuate inequalities unless gender-sensitive communication, participatory governance, and reflexive design are prioritised. These findings highlight the importance of bridging technical expertise with socio-cultural fluency in curriculum design, ensuring future professionals can foster equitable and socially responsive energy systems.

The Renewable Energy Integration strand synthesises insights from other strands, emphasising participatory governance and community engagement. GIA codes A (Rethinking Research Priorities) and I (Rethinking Standards and References) are particularly relevant here, reflecting the need for systemic curricular and policy transformation. Research across Africa and Asia underscores the critical role of women as adopters and facilitators of renewable energy, despite disproportionate barriers (Mahajan & Bandyopadhyay, 2021; Mininni, 2022; Musango & Bassi, 2021). Embedding gender and intersectionality systematically in research, governance, and education ensures transitions that are technically sound and socially just.

Together, the global literature supporting SHAPE and GIA integration confirms that these frameworks are not merely theoretical but are actively shaping inclusive energy education and innovation worldwide. Evidence from diverse contexts, including South Africa, India, Poland, and Canada, demonstrates institutional efforts to embed social science, gender analysis, and participatory approaches, providing concrete examples aligned with the EUA's ambitions. This broad empirical base affirms that the combined SHAPE-GIA approach offers a robust, conceptually grounded, and practically applicable pathway for reimagining energy education as a transformative tool for equity and sustainability.

7. REASSESSING ERIE: THE ROLE OF SHAPE AND GIA

The 2017 EUA ERIE recommendations advocate for interdisciplinary, student-centred, and socially responsive energy curricula that integrate themes such as energy efficiency, smart grids, and renewables into both teaching and research. However, the SHAPE and GIA analysis of MSc programmes in Italy, Germany, Poland, and the UK reveals that this vision has only been partially realised. While there is some progress in promoting interdisciplinarity, particularly in the UK and Germany, this remains uneven and underdeveloped. More notably, gender is almost entirely absent from course design and delivery. Institutions appear to prioritise innovation through technical perspectives, neglecting the social innovations necessary for inclusive energy transitions. This technocratic approach constrains the broader impact of EUA's aspirations and highlights a disconnect between high-level policy ambitions and their practical implementation in academic programmes.

The findings also indicate that although many MSc courses include content on renewable energy and smart systems, they seldom address the socio-cultural dynamics of these transitions. Courses frequently focus on energy technologies and systems modelling but rarely explore critical questions about who controls energy systems, who participates, and who benefits. These issues are central to SHAPE keywords 16 (Energy Citizenship), 8 (Energy Justice), and 17 (Energy Engagement). GIA coding reveals minimal application of methodologies such as D (Analysing Sex), F (How Sex and Gender Interact), and G (Intersectional Approaches). When gender is referenced,

it tends to be limited to vague diversity statements rather than a substantive axis of analysis. Consequently, MSc graduates may possess strong technical skills but lack insight into structural inequalities shaping energy systems, thereby limiting their capacity to design inclusive and equitable solutions.

Despite these limitations, some emerging opportunities exist. Programmes focused on sustainability or transition themes tend to exhibit greater interdisciplinarity and offer more inclusive entry pathways. These courses more closely align with the SHAPE lexicon and occasionally engage social science content beyond economics or policy. Nonetheless, they represent a minority within the sample, and the EUA recommendations do not explicitly emphasise the potential of these approaches. By omitting explicit integration of SHAPE and GIA frameworks, the EUA risks overlooking the strategic role interdisciplinarity can play in advancing gender equity and social transformation in energy education. Without this framing, policy guidance may continue to produce a technically competent yet socially disengaged workforce, inadequately prepared to lead just energy transitions demanded by sustainability imperatives. Overall, the SHAPE and GIA coding highlights a pressing need for structural reform to embed social dimensions consistently in curriculum design, institutional strategy, and policy development.

8. ADVANCING RRI IN ERIE: THE ROLE OF SHAPE AND GIA

The integration of SHAPE and GIA frameworks into the EUA ERIE recommendations operationalises key principles of Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI). As discussed by Burget et al. (2017) and Smallman (2018), RRI emphasises inclusivity, anticipation, reflexivity, and responsiveness in research and innovation processes. This alignment is evident in the SHAPE-GIA coding applied across EUA's four thematic strands, which embeds gender analysis, intersectionality, and social science insights into energy education policy. By moving beyond purely technical considerations, this approach fosters socially responsible and contextually grounded reforms, encouraging innovation co-produced with society in accordance with RRI ideals.

The principle of inclusion is highlighted through GIA codes E (Analysing Gender) and G (Intersectional Approaches) alongside SHAPE keywords 17 (energy engagement), 7 (energy governance), and 16 (energy transition). These codes ensure that marginalised groups, particularly women, are recognised as central to research agendas and educational transformation. EUA recommendations advocating integration of social sciences with engineering disciplines (General Recommendation 1) gain support from empirical studies such as Musango and Bassi (2021), who demonstrate the effectiveness of gender-sensitive systems modelling, and Standal et al. (2020), who provide evidence on participatory leadership in universities. These findings reinforce RRI's call to broaden participation and diversify expertise, underscoring the importance of interdisciplinary and inclusive education tailored to diverse societal needs.

Anticipation and reflexivity are further embedded through SHAPE keywords 8 (energy justice), 6 (energy future/s), and 10 (energy policy), together with GIA codes I (Rethinking Standards and References), A (Rethinking Research Priorities), and K (Rethinking Language and Communication). These facilitate proactive consideration of social impacts and ethical implications in energy innovation. For example, in Renewable Energy Integration, research by Ryser (2019) and Muza and Debnath (2021) highlights how community-led and gender-responsive approaches anticipate

adoption challenges and foster equitable technology uptake. Smallman (2018) critiques traditional deficit models in STEM communication, advocating for participatory knowledge co-production, a practice supported by the SHAPE and GIA frameworks in Smart and Grid Systems education. Together, these insights show that embedding SHAPE and GIA within EUA recommendations not only aligns with RRI principles but provides a practical framework for socially engaged, inclusive, and responsible energy education and innovation.

9. INTERDISCIPLINARITY AS A PATHWAY TO GENDER-EQUITABLE ENERGY TRANSITIONS

The EUA's 2017 Action Agenda identifies interdisciplinarity as essential for transforming energy education, research, and innovation. It recognises that low-carbon energy transitions require systemic engagement with economic, political, social, and cultural dimensions beyond purely technical solutions. Universities are positioned as knowledge integrators, combining engineering, natural sciences, social sciences, and humanities to co-create innovative responses for evolving energy challenges. This approach emphasises breaking down disciplinary silos and amplifying marginalised voices that have historically been underrepresented in energy sectors, reflecting the necessity of broadening participation for more resilient and inclusive energy futures.

Embedding interdisciplinarity structurally within master's and doctoral curricula is critical for this transformation. The EUA promotes project- and challenge-based learning to immerse students in real-world energy problems that demand collaborative, cross-disciplinary approaches. Such pedagogies foster understanding not only of technical systems but also of their social, ethical, and economic contexts. This educational model holds particular promise for attracting and retaining women in energy fields by valuing diverse competencies and communication skills, challenging entrenched gender stereotypes in STEM disciplines. When institutionalised, interdisciplinarity can open pathways for broader participation and enhance innovation capacity.

The SHAPE and GIA frameworks strongly support this interdisciplinary agenda. For example, Recommendation 1 of the General strand aligns with SHAPE keywords 14 (energy social science), 17 (energy engagement), and 4 (energy culture/s), and GIA codes A (Rethinking Research Priorities) and E (Analysing Gender). Empirical studies from Rwanda (Muza & Debnath, 2021) and South Africa (Musango & Bassi, 2021) demonstrate that integrating technical and social perspectives advances innovation and addresses gendered inequities in energy. These findings confirm that interdisciplinarity extends beyond curriculum design to underpin socially responsive, gender-equitable energy transitions.

Interdisciplinary approaches are reinforced across other EUA strands. In Energy Efficiency, Recommendation 4's emphasis on teamwork and real-world projects corresponds with SHAPE keywords 1 (energy behaviour) and 12 (energy practice/s), and GIA codes F (Analysing How Sex and Gender Interact) and G (Intersectional Approaches). Research from Norway (Bentsen et al., 2023) and Kenya (Marshall, 2017) indicates that such models improve engagement and access for women in male-dominated sectors. Similarly, Smart and Grid Systems recommendations call for communication-focused programmes that integrate technical training with social awareness. Studies from South Africa (Musango & Bassi, 2021) and Morocco (Ryser, 2019) show how gender-sensitive and culturally adapted communication enhances acceptance of smart technologies, underscoring the role of interdisciplinarity in inclusive innovation.

The Renewable Energy Integration strand further emphasises interdisciplinarity via Recommendation 6, advocating crossover training such as socioeconomics for engineers or

renewable energy for social scientists. SHAPE keywords 10 (energy policy) and 6 (energy future/s), alongside GIA codes E (Analysing Gender), A (Rethinking Research Priorities), and G (Intersectional Approaches), highlight the value of such cross-domain education. Empirical evidence from India (Mininni, 2022) and Colombia (Mohr, 2021) supports the capacity of interdisciplinary training to equip graduates to navigate gendered barriers and complex societal dynamics. Collectively, the SHAPE and GIA coding reinforces and extends the EUA's Action Agenda by embedding intersectional and equity concerns, confirming that interdisciplinarity enriches participation, relevance, and justice in energy transitions, in line with Responsible Research and Innovation principles and setting a path for inclusive reform in higher education.

10. STRENGTHENING EUA'S FUTURE THROUGH GENDER-RESPONSIVE ERIE

The SHAPE and GIA coding exercises reported here provide the evidence base that informs a variety of recommendations proposed in this section to orient the future of ERIE across European HE institutions. A total of 15 key recommendations are put forward, aimed at reconfiguring curricula, research, and institutional cultures to make them more inclusive, gender-equitable, and socially responsive. Together, these recommendations aim to foster interdisciplinary engagement, challenge entrenched power dynamics, and enhance the participation of women and other underrepresented groups in energy sectors.

10.1 Embed Gender and Intersectionality Across Curricula and Research

Integrating gender and intersectionality throughout energy curricula and research agendas is essential for creating inclusive educational environments and responsive innovation systems. This recommendation builds directly on GIA methodologies A (Rethinking Research Priorities), E (Analysing Gender), and G (Intersectional Approaches), and aligns with SHAPE keywords such as 8 (energy justice), 6 (energy future/s), and 10 (energy policy). Embedding these frameworks across programmes not only exposes students to critical social dimensions of energy transitions but also equips them with the tools to identify and respond to inequities in access, use, and governance of energy systems. This systemic approach ensures that energy professionals are trained to address not only technical challenges but also the societal contexts in which these challenges occur.

The effectiveness of integrating gender and intersectionality into energy curricula and research agendas is well supported by empirical evidence across diverse contexts. Musango and Bassi (2021) demonstrate how embedding gender-sensitive systems thinking into energy planning in South Africa enhances inclusivity and strengthens policy impact, illustrating how gender analysis can shape governance and institutional processes. Similarly, Mahajan and Bandyopadhyay (2021) provide insights from India showing that curricula neglecting gender dimensions inadequately prepare students for real-world energy transitions deeply shaped by inequality, thus limiting their capacity to address social justice in practice. Research by Standal, Talevi, and Westskog (2020) in Norway and the UK further underscores how overlooking gender and intersectionality in smart energy systems perpetuates exclusion and curtails innovation potential. These studies collectively advocate for the mainstreaming of gender analysis and intersectional literacy within energy education and research, positioning them as foundational to achieving equitable and effective energy transitions.

Integrating findings from the broader literature further reinforces the critical need to embed gender and intersectionality systematically in energy education and research. Kowalska et al. (2022) highlight in Poland that gender-differentiated energy behaviours and culturally specific contexts demand curricula that engage deeply with social science perspectives consistent with SHAPE's remit. In Germany, Maier et al. (2019) identify persistent barriers stemming from gender norms and institutional practices that can only be addressed through intersectional methodologies aligned with GIA frameworks. Allen et al. (2019) reveal in the U.S. how women's underrepresentation in leadership and senior authorship roles within energy research publications restricts the diversity of knowledge production and consequently innovation in the field. Studies from other regions, including Pailman and de Groot (2022) in Africa, Peña et al. (2021) in Latin America, and Chen et al. (2015) and Irie and Kawahara (2021) in Asia, consistently point to the marginalisation or superficial treatment of gender and intersectionality in energy curricula and innovation systems. These dynamics reinforce exclusion and limit meaningful engagement. Taken together, these empirical findings highlight that a comprehensive and integrated application of SHAPE and GIA frameworks is essential to prepare energy professionals who can navigate and transform the socio-technical complexities of global energy transitions with a strong orientation toward equity and justice.

10. 2 Foster Interdisciplinary, Collaborative Learning Environments

To reflect the complexity of real-world energy systems, European universities should prioritise the creation of interdisciplinary and collaborative learning environments. This recommendation calls for bridging disciplinary silos by integrating engineering, natural sciences, social sciences, and humanities in energy programmes. The goal is to develop well-rounded professionals capable of navigating both technical and socio-political dimensions of the energy transition. SHAPE keywords 14 (energy social science), 6 (energy future/s), and 12 (energy practice/s), combined with GIA methodologies A (Rethinking Research Priorities), B (Rethinking Concepts and Theories), and H (Engineering Innovation Processes), support this holistic educational shift. Collaborative learning also fosters teamwork, critical thinking, and reflexivity, all vital for addressing the multifaceted challenges of decarbonisation and climate justice.

Empirical evidence underscores the value of interdisciplinary learning across diverse contexts. Kim et al. (2020) demonstrate how project-based courses in South Korea enhance student engagement and develop competencies aligned with sustainability and equity. Ahämer (2021) highlights that challenge-based teaching embedded in transition projects nurtures synthesis of technical, environmental, and social insights. Mohr (2021) shows in Colombia how integrated sustainability education aids understanding of governance, policy, and community needs. Similarly, Kowalska et al. (2022) call for curricula in Poland that combine social science perspectives on gendered energy behaviours with technical knowledge, while Ring et al. (2022) expose how gendered institutional cultures in Sweden hinder interdisciplinarity, signalling a need for reflexive learning aligned with GIA and SHAPE.

Pailman and de Groot (2022) report structural barriers to integrating gender and social justice in interdisciplinary African programmes. Asian studies by Chen et al. (2015) and Irie and Kawahara (2021) further demonstrate that combining environmental literacy with social awareness cultivates holistic competencies. Collectively, these findings reinforce that embedding interdisciplinary, collaborative pedagogies supported by SHAPE and GIA equips graduates with the critical social and technical skills needed to lead complex, equitable, and sustainable energy transitions. This approach bridges STEM and SSH, promotes equity and inclusion, and prepares students to address systemic challenges in climate justice and energy governance.

10.3 Create Mentorship and Networking Initiatives

European universities should establish formal mentorship and networking initiatives to support women and marginalised students in energy-related fields. These programmes can help address gender disparities in academic progression and professional representation by fostering belonging, building confidence, and offering direct pathways into research and industry. Structured mentorship, peer learning, and alumni networks create spaces for guidance, support, and role modelling, which are particularly crucial in male-dominated sectors such as energy. This recommendation aligns with SHAPE keywords 17 (energy engagement), 1 (energy behaviour), and 14 (energy social science), and activates GIA methodologies E (Analysing Gender), F (Analysing How Sex and Gender Interact), and G (Intersectional Approaches), by recognising how different forms of social identity interact to shape opportunity and exclusion.

Empirical evidence underscores the centrality of mentorship and networking in fostering equity within energy education and professions. Mininni (2022) demonstrates how tailored mentoring in rural India strengthens women’s leadership in community-based energy enterprises, while Standal, Talevi, and Westskog (2020) show that formal and informal networks in Norway and the UK enhance women’s visibility and confidence navigating institutional energy systems. Ryser (2019) highlights culturally sensitive mentorship in North Africa increasing women’s participation in energy training and planning. Complementary findings from Allen et al. (2019) reveal persistent gender disparities in U.S. energy research authorship linked to limited mentorship, and Peña et al. (2021) document Latin American education systems’ shortcomings in providing inclusive support, impeding diversity and innovation.

Additional studies confirm the importance of mentorship that is attuned to culture and intersectional issues. Pailman and de Groot (2022) observe that structural and cultural barriers often restrict the effectiveness of African mentorship programmes, reinforcing the need for SHAPE and GIA-informed approaches. Ahmer (2021) similarly notes how culturally relevant mentorship in Pakistan’s renewable energy education promotes women’s engagement and career progression. Collectively, these global findings affirm that well-designed mentorship and networking initiatives are indispensable for building equitable, diverse, and gender-just energy education and research environments.

10.4 Offer Flexible and Inclusive Training Pathways

Higher education institutions across Europe should expand flexible and inclusive training opportunities in energy education to accommodate the diverse needs of learners. These pathways can include hybrid formats, online courses, modular certifications, and living lab models that allow students to engage with real-world sustainability challenges in local contexts. Flexibility helps remove structural barriers faced by women, caregivers, mature students, and those from disadvantaged backgrounds, fostering broader participation in energy programmes. This recommendation aligns with SHAPE keywords 12 (energy practice/s), 16 (energy transition), and 6 (energy future/s), and engages GIA methodologies A (Rethinking Research Priorities), E (Analysing Gender), and G (Intersectional Approaches) by challenging one-size-fits-all models of teaching and recognising the diverse life circumstances that shape educational access.

Empirical research demonstrates the transformative effects of inclusive and flexible pedagogies. Ahämer (2021) shows how ‘learning-by-doing’ approaches within flexible, interdisciplinary formats

empower diverse student groups to develop practical skills while engaging with transition challenges. Mahajan and Bandyopadhyay (2021) provide evidence from India where community-based renewable energy education tailored to socio-cultural contexts sustained women's leadership and participation. Kim et al. (2020) find that adaptable, project-based interdisciplinary courses in South Korea enhance learner agency by allowing students from diverse backgrounds to chart personalised pathways through energy curricula.

Broader literature further confirms the necessity of flexible, inclusive education to address diverse learner needs globally. Pailman and de Groot (2022) highlight that rigid curricula and inflexibility disproportionately exclude women and marginalised groups in African universities, underscoring the need for intersectional approaches consistent with SHAPE and GIA. Peña et al. (2021) document Latin American energy education's lack of gender-sensitive pathways, which limits women's participation and innovation. Rincon-Flores et al. (2020) show how adaptive, community-based energy programmes in Mexico and the U.S. enhance engagement among underrepresented groups by integrating social and technical learning. Standal, Talevi, and Westskog (2020) provide European evidence that flexible, multidisciplinary learning environments promote collaboration and inclusion, crucial for preparing graduates capable of managing complex energy challenges. Together, these studies affirm that flexible and inclusive training formats are critical to achieving equitable, intersectional energy education worldwide.

10.5 Institutionalise Gender-Responsive Leadership and Policy

To advance inclusive energy education, universities must embed gender equity within their institutional governance and strategic frameworks. This involves appointing gender equality officers, integrating gender audits into planning processes, and ensuring gender-balanced representation in decision-making bodies. By adopting SHAPE keywords 7 (energy governance), 14 (energy social science), and 16 (energy transition), and applying GIA codes A (Rethinking Research Priorities), E (Analysing Gender), and H (Engineering Innovation Processes), this recommendation highlights how organisational cultures and leadership practices can be reshaped to address entrenched inequalities. Gender-responsive leadership is not a marginal concern but a foundational condition for fostering systemic inclusion and for ensuring that institutional commitments to sustainability are equitable and participatory.

Empirical research supports the critical role of gender-responsive governance in fostering inclusive energy education. Musango and Bassi (2021) demonstrate in South Africa how gender-responsive systems thinking in institutional energy strategies leads to more inclusive governance and planning. Standal, Talevi, and Westskog (2020) provide evidence from Norway and the UK that institutional policies, leadership practices, and professional norms can either facilitate or constrain women's participation in energy transitions. Mahajan and Bandyopadhyay (2021) show that structural reforms within Indian energy institutions are essential to dismantle male-dominated legacies and open pathways for women's leadership in renewables. These findings confirm that embedding gender equity in university leadership and operations is vital for modelling inclusive, democratic energy governance.

Further global evidence underscores the necessity of institutional gender equity. Allen et al. (2019) highlight persistent gender disparities in leadership and authorship in U.S. energy research, indicating how institutional biases shape innovation and knowledge production. Peña et al. (2021) identify systemic barriers in Latin American energy innovation systems, stressing the need for gender-balanced governance to enhance equity and participation. In African universities, Pailman and de Groot (2022) show that without gender mainstreaming and proactive policies, patriarchal norms and structural constraints limit the success of inclusive curricula and research initiatives. Ring

et al. (2022) examine Swedish engineering education, revealing that informal institutional cultures perpetuate masculine norms hindering women's progression, emphasising the need for gender-responsive leadership reforms aligned with GIA and SHAPE. Together, these studies illustrate that embedding gender equity in governance and leadership is crucial not only for fair representation but also for transforming universities into agents of just and democratic energy transitions.

10.6 Support Project-Based and Participatory Learning

Embedding project-based and participatory learning approaches in energy curricula helps bridge the gap between theoretical knowledge and real-world problem-solving. These approaches emphasise teamwork, active learning, and community engagement, aligning closely with SHAPE keywords 6 (energy futures), 12 (energy practice/s), and 14 (energy social science). GIA codes A (Rethinking Research Priorities), C (Formulating Research Questions), E (Analysing Gender), and H (Engineering Innovation Processes) further support this recommendation by highlighting how inclusive and experiential learning environments can reshape both pedagogical priorities and student outcomes. Collaborative formats such as group projects, applied research with municipalities, and partnerships with industry enable learners to engage with diverse perspectives and prepare them to operate in interdisciplinary and socially embedded energy sectors.

Empirical research affirms the pedagogical and equity benefits of these approaches. Ahämer (2021) shows how project-based coursework in Austria develops students' skills in technical analysis and stakeholder engagement, fostering leadership and practical insight into energy transitions. Kim et al. (2020) find that interdisciplinary teamwork in South Korean MSc programmes enhances student confidence, peer learning, and gender-sensitive collaboration, particularly through real-world projects. Ryser (2019) draws on cases from Morocco and Switzerland to illustrate how participatory student engagement in local energy initiatives deepens civic learning and social inclusion, especially for women and marginalised groups. These studies provide strong evidence that project-based learning is crucial for cultivating socially aware and equity-oriented energy professionals.

Additional global research supports the value of inclusive, experiential education in energy. Kowalska et al. (2022) highlight how curricula integrating social science insights on gendered energy behaviours foster student reflexivity, aligning with SHAPE's interdisciplinary vision. Maier et al. (2019) argue that intersectional pedagogies addressing gender barriers in Germany improve engagement and prepare graduates for complex energy challenges. Standal, Talevi, and Westskog (2020) demonstrate that collaborative learning environments in Norway and the UK enhance women's visibility and confidence, aiding navigation of institutional barriers. Pailman and de Groot (2022) find that participatory learning combined with gender-sensitive approaches in African universities supports inclusion and empowerment of marginalised groups. Together, these findings illustrate that project-based learning not only strengthens technical competencies but also cultivates socially aware, gender-responsive professionals vital for just and effective energy transitions.

10.7 Incorporate Social Justice and Ethics into Energy Education

To ensure that future energy professionals are not only technically proficient but also socially conscious, it is critical to embed themes of ethics, justice, and equity across MSc energy curricula. This aligns with SHAPE keywords 6 (energy futures), 14 (energy social science), and 10 (energy policy), and with GIA codes A (Rethinking Research Priorities), E (Analysing Gender), and G

(Intersectional Approaches), which promote critical examination of how power and identity shape energy access, governance, and outcomes. Integrating these perspectives shifts energy education from a purely technical endeavour to one grounded in critical reflection, social responsibility, and just transitions.

Empirical evidence underscores the urgency and relevance of this approach. Musango and Bassi (2021) demonstrate how gender-sensitive, system-based modelling in South Africa places justice at the heart of energy planning, leading to more inclusive and sustainable strategies. Mininni (2022) highlights how justice-focused energy entrepreneurship education in rural India supports women's agency and socio-economic resilience. Ockwell et al. (2018) stress the need for innovation systems that prioritise social justice in energy transitions in the Global South. Collectively, these studies illustrate that embedding social justice within energy education is central to designing effective, context-responsive, and durable solutions.

Additional research from diverse regions reinforces the imperative to integrate ethics, justice, and equity into curricula. Kowalska et al. (2022) emphasise that social science perspectives on gendered energy behaviours are vital for addressing inequities, aligning with SHAPE's focus on energy justice and futures. Maier et al. (2019) show how intersectional approaches in German STEM education enable critical engagement with power structures influencing energy governance. Allen et al. (2019) reveal gender disparities in U.S. energy research authorship that reflect systemic inequities in knowledge production. In Africa, Pailman and de Groot (2022) find that integrating gender and justice into sustainability curricula fosters more inclusive energy education. These findings collectively support embedding social justice as a core component of energy education to prepare graduates for equitable and resilient global energy transitions.

10.8 Encourage Participatory and Community-Engaged Research

Promoting participatory and community-engaged research within MSc energy programmes is vital for bridging academic knowledge and lived realities. This recommendation aligns with SHAPE keywords 17 (energy engagement), 14 (energy social science), and 7 (energy governance), highlighting the importance of citizen involvement and local knowledge in energy system transformations. It also engages GIA codes C (Formulating Research Questions), G (Intersectional Approaches), and H (Engineering Innovation Processes), encouraging research that emerges through dialogue with diverse communities. Such engagement enhances research relevance, legitimacy, and empowers local actors as co-creators of just and sustainable energy transitions.

Empirical evidence from the gEnesYs SLR database supports this approach. Ryser (2019) shows how participatory projects in Switzerland and Morocco improved student outcomes and trust in energy initiatives. Mohr (2021) documents community co-production of knowledge in Colombia, surfacing gendered and indigenous perspectives often excluded from conventional research. Musango and Bassi (2021) demonstrate the value of participatory modelling informed by intersectional gender frameworks. These studies indicate that inclusive research yields robust, context-sensitive insights and cultivates collaborative skills essential for just energy transitions.

Further global research reinforces the critical role of participatory, gender-responsive research. Kowalska et al. (2022) highlight the importance of local knowledge in understanding gendered household energy behaviours in Poland. Ring et al. (2022) reveal how masculine institutional cultures in Europe restrict participation, stressing the need for inclusive, community-oriented frameworks consistent with SHAPE and GIA. Pailman and de Groot (2022) find that embedding intersectional gender analysis within participatory sustainability education in African universities fosters deeper engagement among marginalised groups. Allen et al. (2019) underscore the

underrepresentation of women in energy research leadership, advocating for inclusive research designs that amplify diverse perspectives. Collectively, these findings confirm that community-engaged research grounded in gender and intersectionality is essential for socially just, contextually relevant energy innovation and for equipping future professionals with necessary collaborative competencies.

10.9 Develop Gender-Sensitive Outreach and Communication Strategies

To enhance inclusivity and equity in energy transitions, universities should develop gender-sensitive outreach and communication strategies that dismantle stereotypes and encourage participation from all social groups. This aligns with SHAPE keywords 17 (energy engagement), 14 (energy social science), and 6 (energy future/s), which emphasise the co-creation of energy systems through inclusive engagement and future-oriented dialogue. It also engages GIA codes E (Analysing Gender), F (Analysing How Sex and Gender Interact), and K (Rethinking Language and Visual Representations), highlighting how gendered representations in education and media shape perceptions of energy careers and technologies. Culturally and socially tailored communication strategies are essential to empower underrepresented groups, especially women and marginalised communities, to participate fully in energy innovation.

Evidence from the gEnesYs SLR database illustrates the impact of such strategies. Ryser (2019) shows that gender-sensitive communication approaches, including storytelling and oral dialogue in rural Morocco, significantly increased women's participation in energy initiatives. Standal, Talevi, and Westskog (2020) find that communication around smart technologies in Norway and the UK often excludes women and older users, leading to reduced adoption and calling for more inclusive messaging. John et al. (2018) demonstrate that youth-led energy initiatives in Nigeria expanded their impact by integrating inclusive messaging and highlighting diverse role models. These studies affirm that communication is not merely information dissemination but a foundational mechanism for equity, engagement, and innovation in energy education and practice.

Additional research highlights the critical role of gender-sensitive communication globally. Allen et al. (2019) reveal how gendered academic publishing practices obscure women's contributions in energy research, stressing the need to reshape language and representation. Peña et al. (2021) identify systemic communication gaps in Latin America that limit participation by failing to reflect diverse social identities. Pailman and de Groot (2022) report that without culturally tailored communication addressing intersectional gender norms, women and marginalised groups remain underrepresented in African energy education and decision-making. Ahmer (2021) documents how culturally sensitive outreach in Pakistan enhances women's engagement in renewable energy. Collectively, these studies confirm that effective and inclusive communication is essential for increasing participation and transforming social norms and power relations in energy systems.

10.10 Highlight Women's Leadership and Contributions in Energy Fields

Increasing the visibility of women in energy is a crucial step towards dismantling the systemic invisibility and marginalisation that have long characterised the sector. By showcasing the leadership, innovation, and resilience of women scientists, engineers, entrepreneurs, and community organisers, universities can challenge dominant narratives and normalise gender-diverse expertise in traditionally male-dominated fields. This recommendation aligns with SHAPE keywords 14 (energy social science), 8 (energy justice), and 1 (energy behaviour), and engages GIA

codes E (Analysing Gender), G (Intersectional Approaches), and J (Rethinking Language and Visual Representations), which help interrogate how representation and visibility shape participation, aspiration, and power in energy transitions.

Empirical evidence from the gEnesYs SLR database supports this approach. Mahajan and Bandyopadhyay (2021) show how public recognition of women's energy entrepreneurship in rural India through storytelling and leadership programmes catalyses broader cultural shifts and opens pathways for others. McArthur et al. (2020), drawing on Canadian data, emphasise that institutional support must be coupled with cultural validation and narrative change, including curriculum content and media representation centring women's contributions. Standal, Talevi, and Westskog (2020) provide European evidence that highlighting women's leadership in community energy projects increases legitimacy, broadens stakeholder buy-in, and fosters trust. Together, these studies demonstrate that recognising and amplifying women's roles is a strategic lever for innovation, collaboration, and meaningful change.

Additional global research confirms the transformative potential of increasing women's visibility across energy education, research, and practice. Allen et al. (2019) reveal persistent underrepresentation of women in leadership roles within U.S. energy research, limiting diversity in knowledge production and reinforcing gendered hierarchies. Peña et al. (2021) document similar patterns in Latin America, where insufficient gender-disaggregated data and inclusive narratives restrict women's recognition and influence in innovation. In Africa, Pailman and de Groot (2022) highlight how culturally tailored efforts to showcase women's leadership in energy education help dismantle stereotypes and empower marginalised groups. Ahmer (2021) illustrates that in Pakistan, elevating women's roles through culturally resonant storytelling enhances community acceptance and participation. Collectively, these findings affirm that promoting women's visibility is vital not only for gender justice but also for driving innovation and legitimacy in the global energy transition.

10.11 Adapt Research Priorities to Reflect Social and Gendered Energy Challenges

Recalibrating research priorities in energy education and innovation to foreground social and gendered challenges is crucial for achieving equitable and sustainable energy transitions. This recommendation urges universities and funding bodies to move beyond narrow technocratic frameworks and adopt interdisciplinary research agendas that reflect the lived realities of diverse populations. It aligns with SHAPE keywords 14 (energy social science), 8 (energy justice), and 7 (energy governance), emphasising governance structures and social dynamics underpinning energy systems. GIA methodologies A (Rethinking Research Priorities), B (Rethinking Concepts and Theories), and E (Analysing Gender) guide institutions in questioning dominant paradigms, uncovering exclusions, and generating equity-centred knowledge.

Evidence from the gEnesYs SLR underscores both the urgency and feasibility of this shift. Musango and Bassi (2021) show how integrating gender analysis into systems modelling in South Africa reveals overlooked barriers to energy access and supports inclusive policy solutions. Łapniewska (2019) critiques European energy efficiency strategies for neglecting gendered household labour, advocating research that values social reproduction and care work. Ockwell et al. (2018), examining multiple Global South countries, demonstrate that sustainable innovation systems must reflect local social structures and gender norms. These studies illustrate how reframing research priorities with SHAPE and GIA perspectives produces actionable, inclusive, and context-sensitive energy solutions, strengthening EUA strategies and supporting the European Research Area's goals of responsible innovation.

Complementary global evidence highlights the importance of gender and intersectionality in shaping research agendas. Allen et al. (2019) reveal how gender disparities in U.S. energy research authorship limit women's career progression and influence which knowledge is prioritised, emphasising the need for intersectional rethinking of research priorities. Peña et al. (2021) find that Latin American energy innovation often excludes gender considerations, resulting in policies that overlook diverse social needs. In Africa, Pailman and de Groot (2022) show that incorporating gender and intersectionality improves the effectiveness and equity of sustainability initiatives. Kowalska et al. (2022) argue for integrating social science insights on gendered energy behaviours within European research to better address inequalities. Collectively, these studies affirm that recalibrating research priorities through SHAPE and GIA frameworks enriches knowledge production and aligns with global commitments to inclusive, responsible innovation and governance.

10.12 Reconfigure Innovation Processes to Address Biases

Innovation in energy systems must be reconfigured to explicitly address embedded biases related to gender, race, and socio-economic status. Traditional innovation pathways often prioritise dominant technical norms and market logics, neglecting the social structures and cultural values shaping access to and impacts of energy technologies. A shift towards inclusive design and participatory innovation is required to systematically incorporate the knowledge, needs, and experiences of marginalised groups. SHAPE keywords 6 (energy futures), 14 (energy social science), and 17 (energy engagement) underscore the necessity of aligning technological development with broader social visions. Complementary GIA methodologies H (Engineering Innovation Processes), E (Analysing Gender), and G (Intersectional Approaches) provide practical strategies for making innovation more reflexive, equitable, and responsive to difference.

Evidence from the gEnesYs SLR supports this reorientation. Ryser (2019) shows how participatory energy initiatives in Morocco and Switzerland, involving women and local communities in design and implementation, improve both social acceptance and technical performance. Standal et al. (2020) argue for intersectional approaches in smart grid design, illustrating how social identity shapes user interaction and exclusion risks. John et al. (2018), examining youth-led energy entrepreneurship in Nigeria, demonstrate that innovation ecosystems ignoring gendered barriers perpetuate inequalities even in grassroots models. These studies make clear that inclusive innovation is both an ethical imperative and a practical necessity for effective energy transitions. Integrating these insights into EUA research and teaching priorities can enhance the resilience, social attunement, and global relevance of Europe's energy innovations.

Further support arises from Allen et al. (2019), who show that women's underrepresentation in leadership roles within U.S. energy research limits the diversity of perspectives shaping technological development. Peña et al. (2021) highlight how Latin American energy innovation systems frequently neglect gender and intersectionality, resulting in exclusionary technologies and policies. In African contexts, Pailman and de Groot (2022) emphasise that incorporating gender and intersectionality into innovation processes enhances the social relevance and sustainability of energy projects. Additionally, Maier et al. (2019) identify persistent gender barriers in German engineering education that foster homogenous innovation cultures, underscoring the importance of GIA's reflexive and intersectional methodologies. Collectively, these studies demonstrate that

integrating SHAPE and GIA frameworks into energy innovation can dismantle systemic biases and foster equitable, context-aware technologies capable of driving socially just transitions.

10.13. Revise Evaluation Standards and Teaching Metrics

To support inclusive and socially responsive energy education, it is essential to revise evaluation standards and metrics for teaching quality, research impact, and institutional success. Current frameworks often prioritise quantitative outputs and technocratic excellence, marginalising collaborative, reflexive, and equity-focused approaches. Reimagining these standards through SHAPE keyword 14 (energy social science) and GIA codes I (Rethinking Standards and References) and J (Rethinking Language and Visual Representations) would enable European universities to value educational models emphasising co-creation, participatory learning, and social accountability. Such frameworks require a broader conception of excellence that rewards diversity of thought, interdisciplinary cooperation, and transformative impacts on learners and communities.

Several studies from the gEnesYs SLR database reinforce the need for this shift. Musango and Bassi (2021) highlight the limitations of traditional evaluation metrics in systems modelling and advocate for gender-sensitive and systems-thinking tools in institutional assessment. Kim and Hwang (2022) show how reflexive, context-sensitive teaching methods in South Korea enhance both student learning and gender equity outcomes despite being undervalued under current academic standards. Mininni (2022), studying women's entrepreneurship in India's rural energy sector, emphasises that institutional success often neglects relational, community-based, and social learning outcomes crucial to inclusive innovation. Adapting EUA evaluation mechanisms to incorporate these goals can foster environments where social responsibility and transformative pedagogy are central to academic excellence.

Complementary perspectives from other regions highlight systemic biases in evaluation practices. Allen et al. (2019) reveal that U.S. energy research undervalues interdisciplinary and gender-focused work, perpetuating barriers for women and socially engaged scholarship. Peña et al. (2021) demonstrate similar marginalisation of social and gender dimensions in Latin American energy innovation metrics, limiting recognition of community-based approaches. In African universities, Pailman and de Groot (2022) stress the importance of integrating gender and intersectional perspectives into institutional evaluations to support inclusive teaching and research. Standal, Talevi, and Westskog (2020) argue that European institutional reward systems often fail to incentivise interdisciplinary and reflexive pedagogies that promote equity and justice. Collectively, these studies underline that reimagining academic standards and evaluation criteria through SHAPE and GIA frameworks is crucial for fostering energy education environments prioritising social responsibility, inclusivity, and transformative impact.

10.14 Design Inclusive Smart Grid and Energy Technology Programmes

As smart grids and digital energy technologies become central to Europe's energy transition, higher education must ensure that training programmes reflect not only technical developments but also the diversity of users, communities, and contexts affected by them. SHAPE keywords 6 (energy futures), 15 (energy storage), and 17 (energy engagement), alongside GIA codes C (Formulating Research Questions), H (Engineering Innovation Processes), and K (Rethinking Language and Visual Representations), highlight the need for inclusive curricula addressing social contexts, user diversity, and cultural factors in technology design and implementation. Programmes should explore how these technologies intersect with everyday life, power structures, and communication practices, shaping adoption and usability rather than treating smart systems as neutral tools.

The literature supports this approach. Ryser (2019), in a comparative study of Morocco and Switzerland, demonstrates that culturally tailored communication improves adoption of smart technologies, particularly among rural women, underscoring the importance of context-sensitive educational content. Standal, Talevi, and Westskog (2020) provide evidence from Norway and the UK showing how gender and social identity influence reception of smart grid innovations, reinforcing the value of training professionals to consider intersectional impacts in energy technology development. John et al. (2018) examine youth-led energy entrepreneurship in Nigeria, revealing that smart innovation may either replicate or challenge existing inequalities depending on how inclusively it is taught and governed. Incorporating these insights into EUA and university programmes supports the development of graduates who are both technically skilled and socially responsive, capable of anticipating and mitigating exclusionary effects of digital energy transitions.

Further global research underscores the importance of integrating social, cultural, and gender perspectives in smart energy education. Allen et al. (2019) highlight gender disparities in U.S. energy research leadership, emphasising that technical innovation in smart grids must be paired with inclusive knowledge production to avoid reinforcing systemic biases. Peña et al. (2021) document similar gender-blind challenges in Latin America, which limit equity and effectiveness in technological adoption. Pailman and de Groot (2022) show that integrating gender and intersectionality in African curricula enhances social relevance and fosters participation among marginalised groups. Maier et al. (2019) illustrate in Germany how gender norms influence the design and reception of energy technologies, highlighting the need for reflexive, interdisciplinary teaching consistent with SHAPE and GIA frameworks. Collectively, these studies confirm that embedding intersectional and socially attuned approaches in smart energy education is essential for preparing professionals equipped to create equitable and inclusive digital energy futures.

10.15 Monitor Progress and Ensure Accountability

Ensuring the long-term impact of gender and intersectionality integration in energy education requires robust monitoring, evaluation, and accountability mechanisms. Institutions should develop transparent systems to track progress across curriculum design, research priorities, staff composition, and student participation. GIA methodologies I (Rethinking Standards and References) and G (Intersectional Approaches), alongside SHAPE keywords 7 (energy governance) and 14 (energy social science), provide a foundation for creating indicators and benchmarks that reflect inclusivity, power dynamics, and structural inequalities. These tools go beyond quantitative metrics to assess the quality of engagement, equity of access, and responsiveness to diverse learners and communities.

Evidence from the gEneSys SLR database supports this approach. Musango and Bassi (2021) demonstrate in South Africa how gender-sensitive systems modelling can inform inclusive governance structures and accountability frameworks incorporating intersectional analysis. Mahajan and Bandyopadhyay (2021) show that institutional inertia in India undermines women's participation in renewable energy unless gender-equity targets and monitoring mechanisms are enforced. Łapniewska (2019) critiques the failure of EU energy policy to meaningfully track and report gender outcomes despite rhetorical commitments. These findings highlight that without systematic evaluation, even well-intended reforms risk becoming symbolic. By operationalising monitoring frameworks rooted in SHAPE and GIA, EUA member institutions can ensure that

progress toward equity is measurable, meaningful, and sustained, turning gender-responsive commitments into institutional norms and long-term cultural change.

Complementing these insights, Allen et al. (2019) emphasise that without rigorous monitoring and accountability frameworks, gender disparities in energy research and education will persist, particularly in academic publishing and leadership roles. Peña et al. (2021) similarly note that Latin American energy innovation systems often lack gender-disaggregated data and clear evaluation benchmarks, undermining efforts to mainstream gender equity. In African contexts, Pailman and de Groot (2022) stress the need for culturally sensitive, intersectional indicators to track inclusion and equity effectively in sustainability education. Standal, Talevi, and Westskog (2020) argue that European institutions must embed gender and intersectionality into governance mechanisms to shift institutional cultures toward greater inclusivity and responsiveness. Together, these studies demonstrate that implementing SHAPE and GIA-informed monitoring systems is essential for transforming gender-responsive policies from symbolic commitments into substantive, enduring change within energy education and innovation.

10.16 Pathways to Just Energy Transitions

Together, these recommendations aim to reconfigure the conceptualisation and delivery of ERIE by drawing on feminist epistemologies, intersectionality, political ecology, and organisational change theories. They emphasise that achieving gender equity requires systemic transformation across curricula, teaching methods, research priorities, and university leadership, reflecting a nuanced understanding of how power operates within energy systems. The SHAPE and GIA analyses suggest that embedding these theoretical foundations into EUA recommendations can enable universities to more effectively operationalise inclusive innovation and equity in energy education.

The fifteen recommendations developed through SHAPE and GIA coding of MSc energy courses and the 2017 EUA ERIE recommendations offer a strategic, evidence-based roadmap for transforming energy education in Europe. They advocate for structural and cultural change in curriculum design, research agendas, institutional governance, and pedagogy, repositioning energy education as a socially embedded process attentive to power relations shaping knowledge, innovation, and access. Grounded in global empirical research and aligned with key European policy priorities such as the Green Deal, the SDGs, and RRI, these recommendations position EUA as a central actor in advancing inclusive, participatory, and democratically accountable energy transitions. By adopting them, member institutions can prepare graduates who are not only technically skilled but also socially conscious and equity-oriented, capable of leading just energy futures through interdisciplinary, feminist-informed, and community-engaged approaches. Thus, the EUA recommendations transcend policy guidance to become practical tools for building equitable, resilient, and socially responsive energy systems.

11. CONCLUSION

This study set out to enhance ERIE in Europe by applying the SHAPE and GIA frameworks to systematically analyse both MSc energy programmes across four countries and the 2017 EUA energy recommendations. The coding of the sampled MSc programmes in Italy, Germany, and the UK revealed notable disciplinary silos and a widespread absence of gender-sensitive and intersectional content, whilst the sample from Poland illustrates a deliberate effort to provide a corrective to more prevalent approaches focused on STEM. Although some programmes in the UK and Germany showed moderate interdisciplinary engagement, most remained rooted in technical

domains. Social science perspectives and gender analysis were rarely integrated into learning outcomes or pedagogy. The use of SHAPE and GIA enabled a structured identification of blind spots, showing how current energy curricula often fall short of preparing students to engage with the social and political dimensions of energy transitions.

The application of GIA methodologies, particularly E (Analysing Gender) and G (Intersectional Approaches), helped uncover how identity-based inequalities are overlooked in programme design. SHAPE coding revealed minimal attention to energy justice, engagement, and governance. These insights highlighted the urgent need to redesign energy education to foster more diverse participation and challenge dominant knowledge systems. The frameworks also demonstrated their scalability and relevance for institutional reform, offering practical guidance for embedding equity and interdisciplinarity at multiple levels of higher education. The findings point to a disconnect between strategic policy objectives and how those objectives are implemented in academic training, underlining the importance of tools such as SHAPE and GIA for bridging that gap.

Extending this analysis, the EUA's 2017 energy recommendations were reviewed across four strategic strands using the same SHAPE and GIA coding. Each recommendation was linked with selected SHAPE keywords and GIA methodologies and then illustrated using peer-reviewed studies drawn from international contexts. This phase confirmed that aligning EUA guidance with SHAPE and GIA not only strengthens its social inclusivity but also grounds policy goals in real-world evidence. The revised recommendations reflect participatory, justice-focused, and collaborative approaches to energy education and research. They promote the integration of gender, intersectionality, and interdisciplinarity into the core of institutional priorities, aligning EUA's agenda with global movements toward equitable energy transitions.

The combined framework also supports the implementation of RRI by advancing inclusion, anticipation, reflexivity, and responsiveness in energy education. The recommendations advocate for co-produced knowledge, inclusive governance, and ethical foresight across teaching and research. While the results are robust, limitations include the capping of codes per recommendation, which may have constrained thematic depth, and the current GIA scope, which could be extended to reflect dimensions such as class, disability, and indigeneity. Nonetheless, the study confirms that SHAPE and GIA provide EUA with a feasible and evidence-based pathway for transforming energy education. This transformation positions European higher education not only as a site of technical excellence but as a driving force for equity, accountability, and innovation in shaping sustainable energy futures.

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe - Culture, creativity and inclusive society - under grant agreement no. 101094326

UK participants in Horizon in Horizon Europe Project (gEneSys) GA. 101094326 is supported by UKRI grant number 10061890 (Imperial College London). Project gEneSys is funded by the European Union under Horizon Europe Grant Agreement No. 101094326. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or UKRI. Neither the European Union nor UKRI can be held responsible for them.

APPENDIX I

A case-study of residential prosuming of solar energy in Norway and the UK (Standal, Talevi and Westskog, 2020) helps illustrate the application of GIA to one specific piece of research on energy transition, as shown in the Table below.

Report on Gender Perspectives into EUA Recommendations on Energy R&I and Education

GIA application to case-study on residential solar prosuming in Norway and the UK

GI Methodology	Key descriptor	Addressed in the case-study Standal, Talevi and Westskog (2020)
A Rethinking Research Priorities and Outcomes	highlighting relevance of gender differences	men more interested in rooftop solar power technology than women (uninterested/reluctant)
B Rethinking Concepts and Theories	unpicking definitions	for some (men/women) becoming 'prosumers' was part of a process to assert themselves as environmentally friendly or energy savvy and engaging in other practices (using public transport; adapting energy consumption)
C Formulating Research Questions	identifying gender-related power hierarchies in energy systems	in Norway and UK men mostly took the initiative and put prosuming on the agenda in their home
D Analysing Sex	highlighting role of biological differences on responses to energy systems/events/processes	both the gendered spaces of the household and the gendered division of labour within it influence how women and men interact with the technology adopted
E Analysing Gender	highlighting role of socio-cultural norms and institutions in maintaining inequality between women and men	role of social practices and gender relations in 'residential prosuming'
F Analysing how Sex and Gender Interact	identifying biological and socio-cultural perspectives on men and women's role and behaviour	gender division of labour in the home conditioned the different ways in which men and women prosumers generally interacted with solar PV technology
G Intersectional Approaches	highlighting role of age, social status, education, ethnicity, race, and geography on access to energy	gender, age, class, ownership type, ethnicity, and language, may combine to thwart empowerment of citizens to manage their own energy consumption and contribute to sustainable supply of energy
H Engineering Innovation Processes	avoiding reproduction of gender inequalities in novel socio-technical energy systems	social perception of prosuming as an exclusively male domain creates barriers to an inclusive decarbonised energy future
I Co-creation and Participatory Research	involving multiple social actors in analysis of problems and generation of solutions	authors note the role of Norwegian Solar Association and UK Solar Energy Society in providing access to techno-economic information on solar energy
J Rethinking Standards and Reference Models	removing gender bias in energy transition to ensure energy availability/affordability	women and men operate in different social fields (workplace, family, community group, neighbourhood) resulting in different dispositions and social positions that can affect their success as prosumers in solar energy
K Rethinking Language and Visual Representations	making explicit the gendered nature of energy transition in ways accessible to non-gender experts/lay people	advertising and information material presented in ways that challenge the idea of prosuming and energy technology as male domains and appeal more to women

Sources: GI (2024); Standal, Talevi, & Westskog (2020)

APPENDIX II

SHAPE/GIA Coding of Most Relevant SLR Journal Articles for Illustrating the EUA ERIE Recommendations

Journal Article	SHAPE* coding and rationale	GIA** coding and rationale
Ahämer, G. (2021) Forward-looking university curricula and enterprises for renewable energies, <i>International Journal Foresight and Innovation Policy</i> , 15 (1): 88-119; http://dx.doi.org/10.1504/IJFIP.2021.10041031	6: encourages student-led thinking on future energy scenarios	B: uses simulation and reflexivity as pedagogical frameworks
	14: applies systems thinking to energy education	C: pedagogy-focused questions on how students conceptualize energy problems
	17: emphasizes participatory teaching in energy and sustainability education	K: focus on visual modelling tools and communication formats
Ahlborg, H. (2019) Changing energy geographies: The political effects of a small-scale electrification project, <i>Geoforum</i> , 102, 99–108; https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoforum.2018.09.016	7: decentralised energy planning and institutional dynamics	C: lived experiences and societal needs
	8: procedural and distributional justice in energy access	E: lived experiences and societal needs
	11: unequal access to electricity in rural Tanzania	G: gender, power, and geography in access to energy
Allen, E., Lyons, H., and Stephens, J. C. (2019) Women's leadership in renewable transformation, energy justice and energy democracy: Redistributing power, <i>Energy Research and Social Science</i> , 57:101233. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2019.101233	2: civic participation and grassroots organising	B: energy transition via social justice lenses
	8: central theme, especially in marginalised communities	G: race, class, and gender in energy activism
	16: energy democracy as a pathway to systemic change	J: community-based participatory research methods
Allison, J. E., McCrory, K., and Oxnevad, I. (2019) Closing the renewable energy gender gap in the United States and Canada: The role of women's professional networking. <i>Energy Research and Social Science</i> , 55: 35–45. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2019.03.011	2: students as co-creators of energy solutions	A: focus on student-centred transformations
	10: grassroots action linked to institutional energy planning	F: differential participation and leadership.
	17: student activism and campus energy governance	G: multiple identities (e.g. race, gender, class) in activism
Arachchi, J. I., and Managi, S. (2021) Preferences for energy sustainability: Different effects of gender on knowledge and importance, <i>Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews</i> , 141: 110767; https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2021.110767	1: public acceptance and behavioural economics	B: challenges assumptions in behavioural economics
	3: consumer-side adoption and attitudes toward new energy tech	D: gender-disaggregated data used in behavioural responses

Report on Gender Perspectives into EUA Recommendations on Energy R&I and Education

	5: energy-saving behaviours across global contexts	G: cultural and gender dimensions of energy behaviour
Assali, A., Khatib, T., and Najjar, A. (2019) Renewable energy awareness among future generation of Palestine; <i>Renewable Energy</i> , 136: 254–263; https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2019.01.007	7: policy gaps in energy planning	C: informed by lived political and social constraints
	8: explores inequities in Palestinian energy access	E: gender roles discussed in community engagement
	10: national energy strategies and local renewables	H: sustainable design tailored to local conditions
Atahau, A. D. R., Sakti, I. M., Huruta, A. D., and Kim, M.S. (2021) Gender and renewable energy integration: The mediating role of green-microfinance, <i>Journal of Cleaner Production</i> , 318: 128536; https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2021.128536	1: investigates behavioural intentions using quantitative survey data	C: Framed around gender, financial capacity, and behavioural theory
	3: consumer decision-making regarding solar PV	D: gender included as a variable influencing adoption patterns
	10: how financial literacy impacts solar panel adoption under regulatory frameworks	F: how gender and financial literacy intersect in solar technology uptake
Atakhanova, Z. and Howie, P. (2022) Women in Kazakhstan’s Energy Industries: Implications for Energy Transition, <i>Energies</i> 15 (13):4540; https://doi.org/10.3390/en15134540	1: household adoption motivations	B: traditional utility models in transition economies
	10: policy impact on household renewable adoption	G: regional and gendered inequalities
	11: energy affordability and inequalities in adoption	H: adoption of energy-efficient home technology
Atif, M., Hossain, M., Alam, M. S., and Goergen, M. (2021) Does board gender diversity affect renewable energy consumption? <i>Journal of Corporate Finance</i> , 66: 101665; https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcorpfin.2020.101665	2: community engagement in smart grid systems	F: differences in digital energy literacy by gender
	17: participatory aspects of new energy tech	G: age, gender, and socioeconomic status in smart grid access
	19: community engagement in smart grid systems	I: equity in smart grid interface design
Baruah, B. (2015) Creating opportunities for women in the renewable energy sector: Findings from India, <i>Feminist Economics</i> , 21(2): 53–76; https://doi.org/10.1080/13545701.2014.990912	4: how cultural expectations shape women's roles in energy	E: women’s exclusion in energy labour markets
	8: women’s exclusion from formal energy sectors	G: how caste, gender, and geography intersect
	13: links women's labour to national energy access goals	K: critiques masculinist imagery in energy policy

Bentsen, E., Skiple, J.K., Gregersen, T., Derempouka, E. and Skjold, T., (2023) In the green? Perceptions of hydrogen production methods among the Norwegian public. <i>Energy Research and Social Science</i> , 97: 102985; https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2023.102985	7: institutional coordination around bioenergy strategy	B: critiques simplifications in techno-economic bioenergy models
	16: public acceptance of bioenergy as part of low-carbon transitions	C: Addresses how public legitimacy influences energy decisions
	18: stakeholder views on carbon mitigation potential	G: regional, cultural, and gender differences in acceptance
Biresselioglu, M. E., Demir, M. H., and Altinci, S. (2022) Understanding the citizen's role in the transition to a smart energy system: Are we ready? <i>Sustainability</i> , 14 (10): 5902, https://doi.org/10.3390/su14105902	1: behavioural factors in energy-saving actions	D: gender as a variable in household energy decision-making
	3: residential electricity users	F: gendered preferences in appliance use and saving intentions
	5: central to household electricity reduction strategies	J: applies psychometric and behavioural tools sensitive to gendered motivations
Bogovac, J., Dodig, D., and Rogić Lugarić, T. (2021) Public-private partnership and circular economy—What Croatian students learn at university, <i>Energies</i> , 14(11), 3261; https://doi.org/10.3390/en14113261	1: how identity and values shape energy practices	A: calls for policy-sensitive design of behaviour change programs
	4: sociocultural meanings of energy saving	F: women more engaged in energy-saving routines
	14: how identity and values shape energy practices	G: how education, age, and gender intersect in household practices
Buechler, S., Vazquez-Garcia, V., Martinez-Molina, K.G., and Sosa-Capistran, D.M. (2020) Patriarchy and (electric) power? A feminist political ecology of solar energy use in Mexico and the United States, <i>Energy Research and Social Science</i> , 70: 101743; https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2020.101743	8: on gendered impacts of climate change and water-energy linkages	E: women's knowledge, agency, and burdens are central
	11: highlights vulnerability in rural and peri-urban communities	G: intersectional feminist framing across water, energy, and gender
	12: everyday household coping strategies	J: combines ethnography with participatory action research
Campos, I., and Marín-González, E. (2020) People in transitions: Energy citizenship, prosumerism and social movements in Europe, <i>Energy Research and Social Science</i> , 69: 101718; https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2020.101718	2: citizens' role in energy communities and prosumer initiatives	B: energy citizenship through justice and democracy
	7: explores local authority and citizen partnerships	F: notes lower female participation in technical and decision-making roles.
	17: motivations and inclusion in citizen energy projects.	G: calls for gender and social inclusion in citizen-led transitions
Chen, S.J., Chou, Y.C., Yen, H.Y., and Chao, Y.L. (2015) Investigating and structural modeling energy literacy of high school students in Taiwan, <i>Energy Efficiency</i> , 8 (4):791–808; https://doi.org/10.1007/s12053-015-9327-5	1: attitudes and intention toward energy-saving measures	D: gender differences measured and discussed in survey results
	3: role of the consumer in driving energy demand reduction	F: gender interacts with household role and energy behaviour

 Report on Gender Perspectives into EJA Recommendations on Energy R&I and Education

	5: central to study on energy-saving behaviour in households	J: employs structural equation modelling that accounts for gendered variables
Chicombo, A.F.F. and Musango, J.K. (2022) Towards a theoretical framework for gendered energy transition at the urban household level: A case of Mozambique, <i>Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews</i> , 157: 112029; https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2021.112029	7: the state's role in energy infrastructure delivery	C: examines built on gendered and spatial access disparities
	8: gendered energy inequality	E: women's experiences in energy access
	11: access to energy in underserved rural areas	G: analyses the impact of gender, geography, and poverty
Clancy, J. S., and Mohlakoana, N. (2020) Gender audits: An approach to engendering energy policy in Nepal, Kenya and Senegal, <i>Energy Research and Social Science</i> , 62: 101378; https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2019.101378	8: gendered distribution of energy burdens and opportunities	A: prioritises empowerment and agency in project design
	11: structural constraints women face in access to modern energy	E: gender central to framing and interpretation
	12: women's energy roles in domestic and productive contexts	G: gender, class, and spatial dimensions
Dagiliūtė, R. (2024) Influence of negative and positive perceptions about renewable energy on intention to use bio—and other renewable energy sources, <i>Environment, Development and Sustainability</i> , 26: 3081–3095; https://doi.org/10.1007/s10668-022-02731-7	1: individual values and willingness to shift practices	B: challenges techno-economic behaviour models by applying value theory
	6: links attitudes to future orientation and climate concerns	D: includes gender-disaggregated analysis
	14: applies sociopsychological theories to energy behaviour	F: links values and motivations to gender identity.
de Wilde, M. (2021) "A Heat Pump Needs a Bit of Care": On maintainability and repairing gender– technology relations', <i>Science, Technology</i>	9: focuses on the use of techno-scientific models in EU climate governance	B: addresses epistemological assumptions in model design
	10: how models shape policy outcomes and frame problems	I: critiques dominant energy modelling standards
	16: models are evaluated for their impact on policymaking in transition	K: how model outputs construct narratives and limit democratic input
Derasid, N.A.C, Tahir, L.M., Musta'amal, A.H., Bakar, Z.A, Mohtaram, N., Rosmin, N., and Ali, M.F. (2021) Knowledge, awareness and understanding of the practice and support policies on	10: focused on aligning policy tools with low-carbon goals	A: suggests shifting policy focus to include local knowledge

renewable energy: Exploring the perspectives of in-service teachers and polytechnics lecturers, <i>Energy Reports</i> , 7: 3410-3427; https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egy.2021.05.031	16: assesses national energy strategy transition	G: inequalities in access and participation, including gender
	18: emphasis on renewable energy uptake in national development	H: investigates technical transition management
Fathallah, J. and Pyakurel, P. (2020) Addressing gender in energy studies, <i>Energy Research and Social Science</i> , 65: 101461; https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2020.101461	8: argues that "empowerment" discourses obscure structural exploitation	E: focus on women's labour and limited gains in bioenergy supply chains
	12: studies the gendered labour of energy farming and biomass product	G: central to the analysis; investigates how gender, class, and agrarian politics interact
	16: questions whether energy transitions reproduce inequities for rural women	K: deconstructs empowerment narratives in energy development programs
Fraune, C. (2015). Gender matters: Women, renewable energy, and citizen participation in Germany, <i>Energy Research and Social Science</i> , 7: 55–65; https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2015.02.005	2: examines public participation in Germany's energy transition	E: central concern in assessing women's inclusion
	4: how culture influences women's roles in transition narratives.	G: integrates gender with sectoral and regional analysis
	8: focus on gender equality in the Energiewende process	K: critiques masculine framings in media and policy discourse
Gonçalves, H.M. and Viegas, A. (2015) Explaining consumer use of renewable energy: determinants and gender and age moderator effects, <i>Journal of Global Scholars of Marketing Science</i> , 25 (3): 198-215; https://doi.org/10.1080/21639159.2015.1041780	1: examines willingness to participate in energy planning	C: research driven by democratic participation concerns
	2: investigates participatory planning in local contexts	F: gender influences willingness and capacity to engage
	14: sociological analysis of perception and participation	J: emphasises participatory and deliberative data collection methods
Hojnik, J., Ruzzier, M., Fabri, S., and Klopčič, A.L. (2021) What you give is what you get: Willingness to pay for green energy, <i>Renewable Energy</i> , 174: 733-746; https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2021.04.037 .	5: focuses on eco-innovation and firm-level strategies	A: calls for inclusive and gender-sensitive business innovation frameworks
	6: business innovation seen as essential for sustainability	E: includes gender among factors affecting firm behaviour and eco-innovation
	19: smart energy and green innovation in industrial contexts	H: innovation is the study's central analytical lens
Irie, N., and Kawahara, N. (2022) Consumer preferences for local renewable electricity production in Japan: A choice experiment, <i>Renewable Energy</i> , 182:1171–1181; https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2021.10.028	16: decarbonization through ICT-based infrastructure	F: how smart city access and benefits vary by gender
	17: citizen participation in smart energy design	G: considers elderly, low-income, and female residents' experiences in digital energy transitions

Report on Gender Perspectives into EUA Recommendations on Energy R&I and Education

	19: smart city development and energy innovation	H: integration of ICT with energy systems
Jaber, J.O., Awad, W., Rahmeh, T.A., Alwaing, A., Al-Lubani, S., Dalu, S.A., Dalabih, A., and Al-Bashir, A. (2017) Renewable energy education in faculties of engineering in Jordan: Relationship between demographics and level of knowledge of senior students', Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews, 73: 452-459; http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2017.01.141	3: survey explores preferences around renewable energy investment	C: grounded in consumer preferences and gender norms
	7: analyses perceptions of national energy decision-making	D: gendered attitudes toward renewable energy investment are central
	10: recommends reforms for broader citizen involvement	I: suggests redesigning policy frameworks to reflect community diversity.
Jin, Q., Simone, A., Olesen, B.W., Holmberg, S.K.M. and Bourdakis, E. (2017) Laboratory study of subjective perceptions to low temperature heating systems with exhaust ventilation in Nordic countries, Science and Technology for the Built Environment, 23 (3): 457-468; https://doi.org/10.1080/23744731.2017.1251266	2: public trust and participation in energy systems	B: conceptualises legitimacy and trust in energy institutions
	4: cultural perceptions in Norway, Sweden, Finland, and Denmark	F: highlights variations in trust and engagement across genders
	7: role of regional planning authorities in sustainable energy systems	G: touches on gender and generational identity in public attitudes
Jirakiattikul, S., Lan, T. T., and Techato, K. (2021) Advancing Households' Sustainable Energy through Gender Attitudes towards Rooftop PV Installations: A Case of the Central Highlands, Vietnam. Sustainability, 13(2), 942. https://doi.org/10.3390/su13020942	8: risks and fairness in biomass energy development	E: interviews include perspectives from women on health and livelihoods
	10: community inclusion in energy decision-making	G: analyses gendered impacts of industrial bioenergy
	11: impacts of large-scale biomass on rural communities	J: uses qualitative risk perception and community-based inquiry
John, T.M, Badejo, J.A., Popoola, S.I., Omole, D.O., Odukoya, J.A., Ajayi, M.A., and Atayero., A.A. (2018) The role of gender on academic performance in STEM-related disciplines: Data from a tertiary institution, Data in Brief (18): 360-374; https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dib.2018.03.052	8: emphasizes social and gender inequities in energy service provision	A: proposes focusing policy and research on women's energy needs
	11: explores gendered impacts of lack of electricity access	E: central to study; highlights how women bear disproportionate burdens
	12: how energy access affects daily activities and livelihoods	G: considers gender, income, and education in access to services
Kacan, E. (2015) Renewable Energy Awareness in Vocational and Technical Education, Renewable Energy, 76: 126-134; https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2014.11.013	1: surveys motivations for energy technology adoption	C: based on behaviour-intention gaps linked to policy

	3: consumer attitudes toward renewables	D: gender incorporated as a demographic variable in survey analysis
	10: evaluates national renewable energy policies	J: uses descriptive and inferential statistics with disaggregated gender data
Karytsas, S. (2018) An Empirical Analysis on Awareness and Intention Adoption of Residential Ground Source Heat Pumps in Greece, <i>Energy Policy</i> , 123:167-179; https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2018.08.001	1: public attitudes toward geothermal energy	C: questions grounded in local socio-cultural acceptance
	10: influence of policy and subsidies on uptake	F: gender influences found in environmental behaviour and awareness
	17: willingness to participate in clean energy use	I: suggests need for gender-sensitive outreach and information strategies
Karytsas, S., and Theodoropoulou, H. (2014) Socioeconomic and demographic factors that influence public's awareness on the different forms of renewable energy sources, <i>Renewable Energy</i> , 71: 480-485; https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2014.05.059	3: on drivers of energy technology use	B: addresses psychological and behavioural models in energy adoption
	5: consumer perceptions of renewable systems	D: gender comparison in technology acceptance and attitudes
	6: captures expectations for sustainable home energy systems	F: Explores how gender shapes environmental motivations and perceptions
Kim, P., Kim, J. S., and Yim, M. (2020) How deliberation changes public opinions on nuclear energy: South Korea's deliberation on closing nuclear reactors, <i>Applied Energy</i> , 270: 115094; https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2020.115094	1: investigates determinants of household energy-saving behaviour	D: gendered differences in energy-saving behaviour are assessed
	3: focus on individual-level energy decision-making	F: considers social roles and gender norms in behaviour
	5: explores consumer strategies for reducing energy use	J: uses disaggregated survey analysis to evaluate gender-sensitive outcomes
Kim, D. and Hwang, J. (2022) Is renewable energy more favourable to diversity than conventional energy sources on RandD performance? <i>Science and Public Policy</i> , 49: 646-658; https://doi.org/10.1093/scipol/scac016	10: analyses energy plans and their framing in official discourse	B: challenges neutrality in energy discourse and reframes via feminist critique
	13: central to national planning objectives	E: how gender is omitted from strategic planning
	18: reviews policies aimed at renewable integration	K: highlights masculine, militarized, and technocratic energy language
	11: examines off-grid solar adoption in energy-poor regions	C: based on unequal adoption outcomes across demographic

Report on Gender Perspectives into EUA Recommendations on Energy R&I and Education

Klege, R. A., Visser, M., Barron, M.F., Clarke, R.P. (2021) Competition and gender in the lab vs field: Experiments from off-grid renewable energy entrepreneurs in Rural Rwanda, <i>Journal of Behavioural and Experimental Economics</i> , 91: 101662; https://doi.org/10.1016/j.socec.2021.101662	12: investigates adoption's impact on household practices	E: gender used to explain differentiated energy access and technology use
	18: off-grid solar seen as a cleaner energy alternative	G: based on unequal adoption outcomes across demographics
Kowalska, N., Brodawka, E., Smoliński, A., and Zarębska, K. (2022) The European Education Initiative as a Mitigation Mechanism for Energy Transition, <i>Energies</i> , 15(18), 6633; https://doi.org/10.3390/en15186633	2: highlights role of women in shaping household energy choices	A: suggests tailoring energy policy to reflect women's roles in domestic energy efficiency
	4: investigates gendered perspectives on energy in rural areas	E: core theme; examines women's roles in shaping domestic energy practices
	12: focuses on behavioural patterns related to heating and lighting	G: links gender with age, education, and household status
Li, X., Liu, D., Han, M. and Li, S. (2022) Consumers' Willingness to Pay for the Solar Photovoltaic System in the Post-Subsidy Era: A Comparative Analysis under an Urban-Rural Divide, <i>Energies</i> , 15(23): 9022; https://www.mdpi.com/1996-1073/15/23/9022	1: energy-saving intentions in urban households	D: examines behavioural differences by gender
	5: study aims to encourage efficient practices	F: connects social norms with behavioural patterns
	14: uses psychological models to assess motivations	J: employs structural equation modelling to map social-psychological pathways
Lieu, J., Sorman, A.H., Johnson, O.W., Virla, L.D., and Ressurreccion, B.P. (2020) Three sides to every story: Gender perspectives in energy transition pathways in Canada, Kenya and Spain, <i>Energy Research and Social Science</i> , 68: 101550, https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2020.101550	2: analyses community energy projects across contexts	A: emphasises socially inclusive energy knowledge systems.
	7: investigates multilevel and hybrid governance models	E: tracks women's participation across energy governance contexts
	8: focuses on fairness, inclusion, and capacity-building in transitions	G: evaluates how gender, class, and geography affect engagement
López-González, L. M., Domenech, T., and Ferrer-Martí, L. (2020) The gendered politics of rural electrification: Education, indigenous communities, and impacts for the Venezuelan Guajira, <i>Energy Research and Social Science</i> , 70: 101776; https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2020.101776	11: focus on access to electricity in isolated rural communities	E: highlights women's active role in energy maintenance and training
	12: how decentralized energy systems alter local practices	G: addresses ethnicity, remoteness, and gender in energy deployment
	18: evaluates implementation of renewable mini-grids	H: advocates inclusive co-design in energy systems
Mahajan, R., and Bandyopadhyay, K. R. (2021) Women entrepreneurship and sustainable development: select case studies from the sustainable energy sector, <i>Journal of Enterprising</i>	4: how local knowledge contests dominant transition narratives	E: explores women's roles, burdens, and agency in biomass value chains

Communities: People and Places in the Global Economy, 15(1): 42-75; https://doi.org/10.1108/JEC-11-2020-0184	8: examines marginalization in biomass energy systems	G: analyses class, caste, gender, and livelihood vulnerability
	16: critiques inequities in green transitions in rural India	K: explores women's roles, burdens, and agency in biomass value chains
Maier, S., Narodoslawsky, M., Borell-Damián, L. et al. (2019) Theory and practice of European co-operative education and training for the support of energy transition, <i>Energy, Sustainability and Society</i> , 9:29; https://doi.org/10.1186/s13705-019-0213-4	2: prepares young women to be informed and engaged energy citizens	A: prioritises inclusive educational innovation
	14: applies social research methods to engineering education	E: investigates the gender gap in technical education and engagement
	17: promotes gender-inclusive education in STEM and energy fields	H: focuses on developing engineering education that integrates gender awareness
Mang-Benza, C. (2021) Many shades of pink in the energy transition: Seeing women in energy extraction, production, distribution, and consumption, <i>Energy Research and Social Science</i> , 73: 101901; https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2020.101901	2: focus on local knowledge and empowerment	A: focus on participatory and inclusive energy transitions
	7: critiques centralized planning from a social justice lens	E: gender highlighted in shaping and accessing energy services
	14: community-level, participatory energy planning methods	G: evaluates power relations across race, class, and gender
Marshall, M., Ockwell, D., and Byrne, R., (2017) Sustainable energy for all or sustainable energy for men? Gender and the construction of identity within climate technology entrepreneurship in Kenya, <i>Progress in Development Studies</i> , 17 (2): 148-172; https://doi.org/10.1177/1464993416688830	3: focuses on affordability, reliability, and gendered needs	E: gender disaggregated data informs understanding of solar use
	8: highlights uneven impacts of energy scarcity	F: women's caregiving roles and energy coping strategies analysed
	11: investigates off-grid solar adoption in informal settlements	J: employs gender-sensitive interviews and participatory approaches
McArthur, S., Stephenson, J., and Jack, M. (2020) Canada's Green New Deal: Forging the socio-political foundations of climate resilient infrastructure? <i>Energy Research and Social Science</i> , 65: 101442; https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2020.101442	8: considers equity and inclusivity in energy governance models	B: evaluates participation by gender, class, and Indigenous identity
	10: analyses regional energy decision-making frameworks	C: study built around democratic inclusion in regional transitions
	17: focus on participatory governance in energy transitions	G: evaluates participation by gender, class, and Indigenous identity
Mehmood, U. (2022) Investigating the linkages of female employer, education expenditures, renewable energy, and CO2 emissions: application of CS-ARD; <i>Environmental Science and Pollution Research</i> , 29: 61277-61282; https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-022-20275-1	7: critiques fragmented policy and regulatory structures	A: calls for energy transitions that prioritize equity and participation
	8: how institutional and political factors exacerbate energy inequity	E: draws attention to women's disempowerment in policy and access
	11: examines barriers to energy access in South Asia	G: frames energy exclusion through gender, class, and region

Report on Gender Perspectives into EUA Recommendations on Energy R&I and Education

Mininni, G. (2022) The Barefoot College ‘eco-village’ approach to women’s entrepreneurship in energy, <i>Environmental Innovation and Societal Transitions</i> , 42: 112-123; https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eist.2021.12.002	4: how energy-related entrepreneurship is embedded in social norms	E: central focus on rural women's energy entrepreneurship
	8: analyses empowerment through distributed renewable technologies	F: highlights differentiated roles, risks, and gains between women and men
	12: everyday energy and economic practices by women	G: considers caste, gender, and economic status in energy access
Mohr, K. (2021) Breaking the Dichotomies: Climate, Coal, and Gender- Paving the Way to a Just Transition, the Example of Colombia, <i>Energies</i> , 14: 5457; https://doi.org/10.3390/en14175457	8: critiques how transitions may reproduce extractivism and inequality	E: highlights gendered impacts of bioenergy expansion in rural territories
	14: uses ethnography and discourse analysis in energy governance contexts	G: links land, gender, and post-conflict dynamic
	16: analyses discourses around Colombia’s post-conflict energy transition	K: deconstructs militaristic and depoliticised narrative
Munien, S. (2014) Rural energy profiles and the role of solar energy in climate change mitigation – a gendered perspective, <i>Agenda</i> , 28:3, 115-126; https://doi.org/10.1080/10130950.2014.932163	8: on gendered vulnerability in urban energy contexts	E: highlights women's experiences and coping strategies
	11: addresses lack of basic energy services in informal settlements	G: frames analysis using gender, age, and socio-economic vulnerability
	12: how gender affects daily energy use and risk	J: uses qualitative methods sensitive to community and gender dynamics
Musango, J. K., and Bassi, A. M. (2021) Towards a Systemic Assessment of Gendered Energy Transition in Urban Households, <i>Energies</i> , 14: 7251; https://doi.org/10.3390/en14217251	7: examines integration of gender in official energy policy frameworks	A: reframes energy planning around gendered outcomes
	8: equity and inclusion in energy modelling and planning	E: core to systemic analysis and participatory mapping
	14: systems mapping used to understand gender in energy planning	I: challenges dominant technocratic approaches and models
Muza, O., and Debnath, R. (2021) Disruptive innovation for inclusive renewable policy in sub-Saharan Africa: A social shaping of technology analysis of appliance uptake in Rwanda, <i>Renewable Energy</i> , 168: 896-912; https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2020.12.091	3: studies household decisions in energy purchases and use	D: considers gender differences in household energy preferences
	5: focus on reducing energy waste and increasing affordability	E: assesses how women’s access to cleaner cooking affects their welfare

	11: investigates drivers of energy access in under-served rural areas	J: uses survey methods to uncover sex-disaggregated insights
Muza, O., and Thomas, V.M. (2022) Cultural norms to support gender equity in energy development: Grounding the productive use agenda in Rwanda, <i>Energy Research and Social Science</i> , 89: 102543; https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2022.102543	1: uses survey methods to uncover sex-disaggregated insights	E: highlights women's responsibilities and health risks
	8: assesses the implications of clean energy solutions for social inclusion	F: gender and social roles shape energy adoption patterns
	12: how household routines and norms shape energy usage	G: income, education, and gender combined in analysis
Ngarava, S., Zhou, L., Ningi, T., Chari, M.M., and Mdiya, L. (2022) Gender and ethnic disparities in energy poverty: The case of South Africa, <i>Energy Policy</i> , 161: 112755; https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2021.112755	3: models fuel choice preferences among households	D: gender as an independent variable in econometric analysis
	11: central concern in urban low-income contexts	F: identifies layered gendered effects in energy choices
	14: applies econometric modelling within a socio-demographic lens	I: suggests current energy metrics fail to reflect nuanced demand drivers
Ockwell, D., Hansen, U.E., Haselip, J., and Nygaard, I. (2018) The uptake and diffusion of solar power in Africa: Socio-cultural and political insights on a rapidly emerging socio-technical transition, <i>Energy Research and Social Science</i> , 4:122-129; https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2018.04.033	7: focus on the politics of low-carbon technology transfer	A: calls for prioritizing needs-based innovation for marginalized communities
	10: critiques the limitations of top-down technology diffusion models	G: explores how systemic inequalities affect access to clean technology
	16: addresses structural challenges in achieving equitable transitions	I: challenges dominant assumptions about knowledge flows and innovation
Osnes, B. (2013) Engaging women's voices through theatre for energy development, <i>Renewable Energy</i> , 49: 185-187; https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2012.01.036	7: explores participatory governance deficits in energy project design	A: argues for inclusive development planning centred on community needs.
	8: assesses fairness in the distribution of energy projects	E: examines how women are marginalized in energy project planning
	10: examines policy gaps in indigenous and rural energy access	G: considers ethnicity, class, and gender in assessing energy access
Paço, A. & Varejão, L. (2010) Factors affecting energy saving behaviour: a prospective research, <i>Journal of Environmental Planning and Management</i> , 53:8: 963-976, https://doi.org/10.1080/09640568.2010.495489	1: examines environmental behaviour among university students	C: research questions include behavioural intent disaggregated by gender
	3: focuses on attitudes toward sustainable consumption	D: gender differences in environmental behaviour are statistically analysed

Report on Gender Perspectives into EUA Recommendations on Energy R&I and Education

	5: examines environmental behaviour among university students	F: assesses how gender roles influence environmental attitudes
Pailman, W., and de Groot, J. (2022) Rethinking education for SDG 7: A framework for embedding gender and critical skills in energy access master's programmes in Africa, <i>Energy Research and Social Science</i> , 90: 102615; https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2022.102615	8: seeks equitable inclusion in modelling practices	E: gender at the core of modelling framework and participation
	9: Uses feminist-informed, participatory modelling approaches	G: models include diverse positionalities, including gender, age, and class
	14: focus on integrating gender into energy system modelling	I: Questions traditional assumptions in energy systems modelling
Peña, M., Olmedo-Torre, N., de les Valls, E.M., and Lusa, A. (2021) Introducing and Evaluating the Effective Inclusion of Gender Dimension in STEM Higher Education, <i>Sustainability</i> , 13(9):4994. https://doi.org/10.3390/su13094994	8: highlights justice dimensions in governance mechanisms	C: focuses on inclusiveness and public representation in energy planning
	10: analyses stakeholder inclusion in regional energy planning	E: notes the underrepresentation of women and other groups in policy spaces
	17: investigates public involvement in participatory energy processes	K: investigates how procedural justice is framed in energy discourse
Ramisio, P. J., Pinto, L.C., Almeida, M. (2024) The need for scientific-area-related indicators for effective energy planning in higher education institutions, <i>Heliyon</i> , 10 (11): e31688; https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2024.e31688	6: focus on how youth conceptualize and participate in shaping future energy systems	A: highlights the importance of including youth perspectives in energy transition strategies
	14: integrates social values and participatory methodologies in educational contexts	C: focus on understanding students' energy perceptions through participatory method
	17: examines university students' active role in sustainability and energy transition	K: emphasizes storytelling and visual tools to capture student imaginaries
Rincón-Flores, E. G., Mena, J., Ramírez-Montoya, M. S., and Méndez, R.R. (2020) The use of gamification in xMOOCs about energy: Effects and predictive models for participants' learning, <i>Australasian Journal of Educational Technology</i> , 36(2); https://doi.org/10.14742/ajet.4818	4: how cultural context shapes sustainability learning	C: focused on pedagogical interventions
	6: focus on empowering youth for climate-resilient societies	F: touches on demographic diversity in STEM education
	17: examines student participation in sustainability education	K: uses learning analytics to reframe student empowerment

Ring, M., Wilson, E., Ruwnapura, K.N., and Gay-Antaki, M. (2022) Just energy transitions? Energy policy and the adoption of clean energy technology by households in Sweden, <i>Energy Research and Social Science</i> , 91: 102727; https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2022.102727	2: promotes inclusive citizen-led decision-making	C: questions shaped by concern with democratic inclusion and representation
	7: focuses on the intersection of public participation and local authority	G: explores dynamics of power, gender, and voice in public forums
	17: explores deliberative democratic practices in local energy planning	K: examines how narratives include/exclude certain identities
Ryser, S. (2019) The Anti-Politics Machine of Green Energy Development: The Moroccan Solar Project in Ouarzazate and Its Impact on Gendered Local Communities, <i>Land</i> , 8(6): 100: https://doi.org/10.3390/land8060100	2: explores local participation in renewable energy projects	E: Women's marginalisation in participatory processes is central
	8: addresses inequities in benefit-sharing of solar initiatives	G: explores how class, gender, and location shape project impacts.
	16: examines governance and resistance in clean energy deployment	K: analyses discourse around energy transitions in Moroccan context
Sikka, T. (2018) Technology, gender, and climate change: A feminist examination of climate technologies, <i>Societies</i> , 8(4): 109; https://doi.org/10.3390/soc8040109	8: critiques development narratives that ignore women's agency	B: challenges top-down, techno-centric views of energy transitions
	11: focuses on women's access to clean cooking energy	E: central to the argument; women's roles and experiences are thoroughly examined
	12: explores the everyday energy use of women and the social roles embedded in those practices	G: looks at class, caste, and regional disparities alongside gender
Standal, K., Talevi, M., and Westskog, H. (2020) Engaging men and women in energy production in Norway and the United Kingdom: The significance of social practices and gender relations, <i>Energy Research and Social Science</i> , 60: 101383; https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2019.101338	2: Investigates the emergence of energy citizenship through community energy.	B: proposes new framings of citizenship beyond consumption
	8: addresses gendered dimensions of energy access and engagement	E: gender shapes different forms of participation and responsibility in energy initiative
	17: explores how citizens participate in shaping local energy systems	G: looks at how gender intersects with institutional and geographic contexts
Łapniewska, Z. (2019) Energy, equality and sustainability? European electricity cooperatives from a gender perspective, <i>Energy Research and Social Science</i> , 57: 101247; https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2019.101247	2: advocates for feminist energy citizenship	E: core feminist critique of energy transition policies
	4: examines dominant masculine energy norms	G: Addresses how gender intersects with labour, care, and ecology
	8: focuses on systemic exclusion of women in the energy transition	K: deconstructs masculine framings and proposes alternative narratives
	8: focus on equity in clean energy access and gendered implications	E: central to health, labour, and social impact discussions

Report on Gender Perspectives into EUA Recommendations on Energy R&I and Education

Wiese, K. (2020) Energy 4 all? Investigating gendered energy justice implications of community-based micro-hydropower cooperatives in Ethiopia, <i>Innovation: The European Journal of Social Science Research</i> , 33:2, 194-217; https://doi.org/10.1080/13511610.2020.1745059	11: examines household transitions from traditional fuels to modern energy	F: demonstrates gendered burdens and decision-making within the household
	12: highlights cooking practices and health impacts	J: uses life-cycle thinking and gender-disaggregated surveys
Zaman, Q.U., Wang, Z., Zaman, S., and Rasool, S.F. (2021) Investigating the nexus between education expenditure, female employers, renewable energy consumption and CO2 emission: Evidence from China, <i>Journal of Cleaner Production</i> , 312: 127824; https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2021.127824	1: investigates behavioural intentions around renewable energy adoption	C: builds questions around behaviour and demographic variables
	10: links individual perceptions to policy effectiveness	D: gender included as a factor in survey analysis
	18: focus on solar and renewable integration in cities	F: identifies how motivations vary by gender
Zhang, A.T., Patnaik, S., Jha, S., Agrawal, S., Gould, C.F., and Urpelainen, J. (2022) Evidence of multi-dimensional gender inequality in energy services from a large-scale household survey in India, <i>Nature Energy</i> 7: 698-707; https://doi.org/10.1038/s41560-022-01044-3	4: investigates local norms influencing solar adoption in rural communities	A: advocates for community-led and gender-aware solar deployment
	11: focus on access disparities and solutions through decentralisation	E: women's voices and constraints are foregrounded in technology adoption
	18: examines household solar as a sustainable option	G: connects caste, gender, and income to energy access
Zyadin, A., Puhakka, A., Holder, P., Ahponen, P., and Pelkonen, P. (2014) The relative importance of home, school, and traditional mass media sources in elevating youth energy awareness, <i>Applied Energy</i> , 114: 409-416; http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2013.09.072	8: highlights health and workload implications for women using biomass	E: central to the analysis of firewood collection and energy burdens.
	11: focuses on energy access challenges in rural households	F: women's role as primary biomass users drives differentiated impacts
	12: analyses domestic wood consumption and its social impacts	G: evaluates gender in relation to education, income, and geographic context
Żuk, P., and Paczeński, A. (2020) Sustainable development, energy transition, and climate challenges in the context of gender: The framework of gender determinants of environmental orientation in Poland, <i>Sustainability</i> , 12(21): 9231; https://doi.org/10.3390/su12219214	8: critiques exclusionary and elite-driven policy processes	B: introduces postcolonial and justice-based theoretical lenses
	14: uses political sociology to explore public trust and resistance	G: considers how class and rural-urban divides structure energy transitions

	16: examines how Poland's transition intersects with socio-political values	K: unpacks the political language shaping Polish energy debates
*Numbered SHAPE Keywords: 1= Energy behaviour; 2= Energy citizen(ship); 3= Energy consumer; 4= Energy culture(s); 5= Energy efficiency; 6 = Energy future(s); 7= Energy governance; 8= Energy justice; 9= Energy models; 10= Energy policy; 11= Energy poverty; 12= Energy practice(s); 13= Energy security; 14= Energy social science; 15= Energy storage; 16= Energy transition; 17= Energy engagement; 18= Low-carbon energy; 19= Smart; 20= Socio-technical		
** Lettered GIA Methodologies: A= Rethinking research priorities and outcomes; B= Rethinking concepts and theories; C= Formulating research questions; D= Analysing sex; E= Analysing gender; F= Analysing how gender and sex interact; G= Intersectional approaches; H= Engineering innovation processes; I – Co-creation and participation; J= Rethinking Standards and References; K= Rethinking Language and Visual Representations		
Source: Compiled from EUA (2017), SHAPE (2017) and GI (gEneSys, 2024) by gEneSys partners in the UK		

APPENDIX III

Table A - EUA ERIE General Recommendations: SHAPE/GIA Coded and Illustrated

No.	General Recommendations	SHAPE (KN ¹)	GIA (ML ²)	Supporting gEneSys SLR articles
1	Social sciences and humanities should be integrated with technological sciences to solve complex problems	14, 16, 20	B, E, H, I	Mohr (2021); Musango & Bassi (2021); Mininni (2022)
2	University leadership should support multidisciplinary activity	14, 16, 20	A, E, B, H	Lieu et al. (2020); Musango & Bassi (2021); Mininni (2022);
3	Increase funding for master's/research projects in new areas	6, 16, 10	A, E, F	Ryser (2019); Kim et al. (2020); Atif et al. (2021)
4	Multidisciplinary research: potential publication in lower-impact journals	6, 14, 16	A, E, I, J	Fraune (2015); Allen et al. (2019); Musango & Bassi (2021)
5	Integrate state-of-the-art energy research into educational programmes by: Master's theses; facilitating invitations for students to attend outstanding research; remote access to labs and unique research facilities	6, 10, 14	A, C, E, H	Ryser (2019); Kim et al. (2020); Atif et al. (2021)
6	Adapt teaching methodologies for future energy professionals integrating project-based courses with an integrated approach, including teamwork (groups of 3-10 students), visits, and work with companies or municipalities on real world projects	6, 12, 14	A, C, E, H	Ryser (2019); Kim et al. (2020); Ahämer (2021)
7	Integration of innovation and entrepreneurship	6, 12, 17	C, E, H, G	John et al. (2018); Mahajan & Bandyopadhyay (2021); Mininni (2022)
8	Skills versus knowledge orientation	6, 12, 14	A, C, E, H	Munien (2014); Ryser (2019); Ahämer (2021)

 Report on Gender Perspectives into EUA Recommendations on Energy R&I and Education

9	Alternative training, with students spending 50% of their time in industry	6, 12, 17	A, C, E, H	John et al. (2018); Kim et al. (2020); Ahämer (2021)
10	MOOCs (without ECTS) for students and citizens	2, 14, 17	E, C, I, K	Rincon-Flores et al. (2020); Kim et al. (2020); Standal et al. (2020)
11	Basic and applied research should not be understood as a dichotomy – solving application problems often requires an understanding of and solutions using the fundamentals. It's an iterative process	6, 14, 20	B, E, H, J	Mohr (2021), Musango & Bassi (2021); Mininni (2022)
12	Communication and cooperation between students and university leadership	2, 14, 17	E, F, I, K	Standal et al. (2020); Atif et al. (2021); Ahämer (2021)
13	Use online labs for distance learning, involve students/campus living labs	6, 17, 20	A, E, H, K	Kim et al. (2020); Standal et al. (2020); Ahämer (2021)
14	Create structures such as Social Science labs for sustainable energy connecting people and ICT tools	14, 17, 20	E, G, H, I	Standal et al. (2020); Mohr (2021); Musango & Bassi (2021)
15	University organisation: establish profiling thresholds (e.g. expected % of social scientists, engineers etc.) when designing multidisciplinary courses	14, 16, 20	E, B, G, I	Mohr (2021); Mininni (2022); Musango & Bassi (2021)
16	Universities should support social transformation co-construction, co-working: industry, government, civil society, campus facilities and human capital to be used for living labs (multi/interdisciplinary/holistic approach), greater freedom to implement the emergence of green teams (managing energy, waste, urban concern and communication, beyond energy and towards sustainability, provide a front desk for energy	16, 17, 20	A, E, G, H	Standal et al. (2020); Mohr (2021); Musango & Bassi (2021)
17	Bottom-up approach should be supported by university management. It takes time to work together (ca. 4 years), and needs: trust, dedication, money and flexibility	12, 17, 14	A, E, F, G	Standal et al. (2020); Mohr (2021); Mininni (2022)
18	Address Intellectual Propriety Rights (IPRs)	7, 10, 16	A, E, G, I	Ockwell et al. (2018); Mahajan & Bandyopadhyay (2021); Mininni (2022)
19	Next-generation students have different learning needs and relational behaviour. Now more content is available online there is an increasing need for guidance and mentoring from teachers	12, 14, 17	E, C, F, H	Ryser (2019); Kim et al. (2020); Ahämer (2021)

	rather than content provision. New generations learn more in groups and are highly collaborative			
20	Develop innovative educational modules for different student types: from online educational modules for next-generation students, to more professional education for current industry/company managers (i.e. Energy business MBAs). Evolution of current education to more problem-based courses in Energy engineering	6, 14, 17	A, C, E, H	Kim et al. (2020); Atif et al. (2021); Ahämer (2021)
21	Set demonstration off-campus	12, 14, 17	A, E, G, H	Ryser (2019); Standal et al. (2020); Mohr (2021)
22	Connect to existing repositories	6, 10, 14	A, C, E, I	Karytsas & Theodoropoulou (2014); McArthur et al. (2020); Musango & Bassi (2021)
23	Cross border projects require the involvement of experts from different disciplines	7, 14, 16	A, B, E, G	Ockwell et al. (2018); McArthur et al. (2020); Mohr (2021)
24	Develop tools such as the Decision Support System	7, 9, 14	A, E, I, H	McArthur et al. (2020); Musango & Bassi (2021); Pailman & de Groot (2022)
25	Address energy and climate together (energy transition)	8, 14, 16	A, B, E, G	Mahajan & Bandyopadhyay (2021); Mohr (2021); Musango & Bassi (2021)
26	Implement a transversal approach for future energy education: make it theme-based (energy, Maths and social sciences) and focused on actors (industry, government, research institutes, financial sector)	7, 14, 16	A, B, E, H	McArthur et al. (2020); Musango & Bassi (2021); Mininni (2022)
27	Develop new Energy, Environment and Society master's programmes	6, 14, 16	A, B, C, E	Maier et al. (2019); Musango & Bassi (2021); Mininni (2022)
28	Develop practices to engage citizens: weekly informal lunches (open to all, free of charge), newsletters, living labs, workshops, representation at municipal and other forums, social debates	2, 14, 17	A, E, G, K	Standal et al. (2020); Mohr (2021); Muza & Debnath (2021)
29	University-based research to integrate more strongly with market needs	6, 10, 12	A, E, G, H	John et al. (2018); Mahajan & Bandyopadhyay (2021); Musango & Bassi (2021)
30	National Rectors Conferences should consider promoting the development of joint Energy Transition master's programmes at universities in their countries	6, 14, 16	A, B, C, E	Maier et al. (2019); Musango & Bassi (2021); Mininni (2022)
31	Universities need to strengthen their post-doc capacities in this field to achieve the future breakthroughs needed in basic research	6, 14, 16	A, B, C, E	Maier et al. (2019); Kim et al. (2020); Atif et al. (2021)
Key: 1KN= Keyword Number; 2ML= Methodology Letter				
SHAPE Keyword Number				

Report on Gender Perspectives into EUA Recommendations on Energy R&I and Education

2= Energy citizen(ship); 6= Energy future(s); 7 = Energy governance; 8= Energy justice; 9= Energy models; 10= Energy policy; 12= Energy practice(s); 14= Energy social science; 16= Energy transition; 17= Energy engagement; 20= Sociotechnical

GIA Methodology Letter

A= Rethinking Research Priorities and Outcomes; B= Rethinking Concepts and Theories; C= Formulating Research Questions; E= Analysing Gender; F= Analysing How Gender and Sex Interact; G= Intersectional Approaches; H= Engineering Innovation Processes; I= Co-creation and Participatory Research; J= Rethinking Standards and References; K= Rethinking Language and Visual Representations

Table B - EUA ERIE Recommendations on Energy Efficiency: SHAPE/GIA Coded and Illustrated

No.	Recommendations Energy Efficiency	SHAPE (KN ¹)	GIA (ML ²)	Supporting gEneSys SLR articles
1	Design open-source tools for energy consumption analysis	5, 9, 14,	A, E, H, I	McArthur et al. (2020); Musango & Bassi (2021); Pailman & de Groot (2022)
2	Reduce energy consumption in houses	1, 5, 12	A, E, F, G	Łapniewska (2019); Kim & Hwang (2022); Kowalska et al. (2022)
3	Convince stakeholders to invest in new concepts	7, 10, 17	A, E, G, H	John et al. (2018); Mahajan & Bandyopadhyay (2021); Musango & Bassi (2021)
4	Remove non-technical barriers	7, 8, 14	A, E, G, I	Ockwell et al. (2018); Mahajan & Bandyopadhyay (2021); Mininni (2022)
5	Make building energy reports easy	5, 9, 14	A, E, H, I	McArthur et al. (2020); Musango & Bassi (2021); Pailman & de Groot (2022)
6	Include social aspects and architecture in engineering, e.g. Techno-anthropology	12, 14, 20	B, E, G, H	Fraune (2015); Mohr (2021); Musango & Bassi (2021)
7	Link energy use with comfort and design	5, 12, 20	B, E, G, H	Chen et al. (2015); McArthur et al. (2020); Li et al. (2022)
8	Monitor education indicators: define Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) for management systems to ensure sustainable development and energy efficiency	5, 10, 14	A, E, I, J	Chen et al. (2015); Clancy & Mohlakoana (2020); McArthur et al. (2020)

9	University leadership should take ownership of campus energy sustainability	7, 14, 16	A, E, G, H	Standal et al. (2020); Ahämer (2021); Musango & Bassi (2021)
10	Develop guidelines to assess campus energy sustainability (and rank them)	7, 9, 16	A, E, H, I	McArthur et al. (2020); Musango & Bassi (2021); Pailman & de Groot (2022)
11	Develop campus energy manager profiles	7, 12, 16	A, B, E, H	Standal et al. (2020); Ahämer (2021); Musango & Bassi (2021)
12	Complement research on new buildings by retrofitting existing constructions	5, 12, 20	A, E, G, H	Chen et al. (2015); McArthur et al. (2020); Li et al. (2022)
13	Technologies and services have to be conceived in an integrated manner to provide added value - integration and a systemic approach is key	14, 16, 20	B, E, G, H	Fraune (2015); Mohr (2021); Musango & Bassi (2021)
14	Place importance on business models	6, 10, 12	A, E, G, H	John et al. (2018); Mahajan & Bandyopadhyay (2021); Musango & Bassi (2021)
Key: 1KN= Keyword Number; 2ML= Methodology Letter				
SHAPE Keyword Number 1= Energy behaviour; 5= Energy efficiency; 6= Energy future(s); 7 = Energy governance; 8= Energy justice; 9= Energy models; 10= Energy policy; 12= Energy practice(s); 14= Energy social science; 16= Energy transition; 17=Energy engagement; 20= Sociotechnical				
GIA Methodology Letter A= Rethinking Research Priorities and Outcomes; B= Rethinking Concepts and Theories; E= Analysing Gender; F= Analysing How Gender and Sex Interact; G= Intersectional Approaches; H= Engineering Innovation Processes; I= Co-creation and Participatory Research; J= Rethinking Standards and References				

Table C - EUA ERIE Recommendations on Smart & Grid Systems: SHAPE/GIA Coded and Illustrated

No.	Recommendations Smart & Grid Systems	SHAPE (KN ¹)	GIA (ML ²)	Supporting gEneSys SLR articles
1	Test systems with different energy carriers (natural gas, oil, hot water, steam, etc.)	9, 15, 18	E, B, H, I	John et al. (2018) ; Mahajan & Bandyopadhyay (2021); Musango & Bassi (2021)
2	Emerging synchronised measurements can contribute to more accurate monitoring and control, even extending from wide areas to local distribution systems	9, 13, 15	A, E, H, I	John et al. (2018); Mahajan & Bandyopadhyay (2021); Musango & Bassi (2021)
3	There is a need for training on effectively communicating smart meters and energy use to end-users	12, 14, 17	C, E, F, K	Ryser (2019); Kim et al. (2020); Standal et al. (2020)
4	The new field of education has to exceed standard dissemination	6, 14, 17	A, E, H, K	Ryser (2019); Standal et al. (2020); Ahämer (2021)
5	Establish new master's programmes on how to communicate emerging technologies such as smart	6, 14, 17	C, E, F, H	Ryser (2019); Kim, Kim & Yim (2020); Standal et al. (2020)

Report on Gender Perspectives into EUA Recommendations on Energy R&I and Education

	metering, which may have a strong impact on the overall energy system, to end-users			
6	Research the impact of different interfaces to inform different types of consumers	3, 14, 17	C, E, F, K	Ryser (2019); Kim et al. (2020); Standal et al. (2020)
7	Pay attention to the scale of the system addressed and whether energy systems can be analysed bottom up/top down	9, 14, 20	A, B, E, H	Mohr (2021); Musango & Bassi (2021); Mininni (2022)
8	Train system experts	6, 14, 18	A, C, E, H	Kim et al. (2020); Atif et al. (2021); Mininni (2022)
9	Good examples of cross-disciplinary challenges include: energy storage, efficiency and management, spatial, urban and solar application	5, 15, 20	B, E, G, H	Chen et al. (2015); Mohr (2021); Musango & Bassi (2021)
10	Energy storage technologies and grid management should always be very innovative and multi-disciplinary due to their future-oriented, social perspectives	15, 18, 20	B, E, G, H	Ryser (2019); Kim et al. (2020); Ahämer (2021)
11	Provide hands-on interdisciplinary options to impart skills for building and component design (e.g. planning, measurement, app development)	6, 12, 14	A, C, E, H	Chen et al. (2015); Ryser (2019); Mohr (2021)
12	Connect with smart city research: scale-up from campus to city	7, 14, 20	A, E, G, H	McArthur et al. (2020); Standal et al. (2020); Musango & Bassi (2021)
Key: 1KN= Keyword Number; 2ML= Methodology Letter				
SHAPE Keyword Number 3= Energy consumer; 5= Energy efficiency; 6= Energy future(s); 7 = Energy governance; 9= Energy models; 12= Energy practice(s); 13 = Energy security; 14= Energy social science; 15 = Energy storage; 17= Energy engagement; 18 = Low-carbon energy; 20= Sociotechnical				
GIA Methodology Letter A= Rethinking Research Priorities and Outcomes; B= Rethinking Concepts and Theories; C = Formulating Research Questions; E= Analysing Gender; F= Analysing How Gender and Sex Interact; G= Intersectional Approaches; H= Engineering Innovation Processes; I= Co-creation and Participatory Research; K= Rethinking Language and Visual Representation				

Table D - EUA ERIE Recommendations on Renewable Energy Integratin: SHAPE/GIA Coded and Illustrated

No.	Recommendations on Renewable Energy Integration	SHAPE (KN ¹)	GIA (ML ²)	Supporting gEneSys SLR articles
1	Involve residents, property owners and citizens through activities and popular events	2, 14, 17	A, E, G, K	Standal et al. (2020); Mohr (2021); Muza & Debnath (2021)
2	Transfer knowledge from oil- and gas- based energy systems to sustainable approach and use of renewable resources	7, 16, 18	A, B, E, G	Ockwell et al. (2018); Mahajan & Bandyopadhyay (2021); Musango & Bassi (2021)
3	Research the effectiveness of integrating and auctioning renewables	7, 10, 16	A, E, G, I	Ockwell et al. (2018); McArthur et al. (2020); Mahajan & Bandyopadhyay (2021)
4	Try to create test cases of solutions adapted to future legislation	7, 10, 16	A, E, H, I	Ockwell et al. (2018); McArthur et al. (2020); Mahajan & Bandyopadhyay (2021)
5	Work on standardisation and university representation at standardisation bodies	7, 10, 14	A, E, H, I	Ockwell et al. (2018); Maier et al. (2019); Musango & Bassi (2021)
6	Develop postgraduate studies including socioeconomics for engineers, psychology for engineers, renewable energies for social scientists, etc. (as in MBAs)	6, 14, 16	A, B, C, E	Maier et al. (2019); Musango & Bassi (2021); Mininni (2022)
7	Research new materials (abundance, cost efficiency, environmental aspects)	5, 6, 18	A, B, E, H	Fraune (2015); Mahajan & Bandyopadhyay (2021); Musango & Bassi (2021)
Key: 1KN= Keyword Number; 2ML= Methodology Letter				
SHAPE Keyword Number 2= Energy citizen(ship); 5= Energy efficiency; 6= Energy future(s); 7 = Energy governance; 10= Energy policy; 14= Energy social science; 16= Energy transition; 18 = Low-carbon energy				
GIA Methodology Letter A= Rethinking Research Priorities and Outcomes; B= Rethinking Concepts and Theories; C = Formulating Research Questions; E= Analysing Gender; G= Intersectional Approaches; H= Engineering Innovation Processes; I= Co-creation and Participatory Research; K= Rethinking Language and Visual Representation				